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**UNDERSTANDING THE ORIENTAL PERSPECTIVE OF GENDER EQUALITY:
INITIAL SURVEY OF FILIPINO RESPONDENTS**

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Acceptance Page:

This thesis titled: “**UNDERSTANDING THE ORIENTAL PERSPECTIVE OF GENDER EQUALITY: INITIAL SURVEY OF FILIPINO RESPONDENTS**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of ASEAN Studies.

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Biographical Sketch

Liliha Chelle D. Baleña was born and raised in Iloilo. Her formal educational history began at the Miagao Central Elementary School, Miagao, Iloilo, where she completed her primary education. She continued her secondary education at the University of the Philippines High School in Iloilo City. Later, she pursued a bachelor's degree in Applied Mathematics at the University of the Philippines in the Visayas, Miagao, Iloilo. Afterwards, she pursued her Master of Science degree in ASEAN Studies at the University of the Philippines Open University in Los Baños, Laguna.

Following her graduation with a bachelor's degree, Baleña embarked on a career in government service with the Philippine Health Insurance Corporation (PhilHealth), the Philippines' national health insurance provider. In her role, she was responsible for data extraction, processing, analysis, presentation, and release for a span of eight years. Additionally, she served as a member of the Gender and Development (GAD) Committee and the National Statistics Month (NSM) Committee within the organization. Simultaneously, she was entrusted with the position of PRAISE Secretariat for the agency. Thereafter, she made a short stint with the Philippine Statistical Authority regional office in Iloilo City as Statistical Specialist II, before embarking on a new career in the private sector. Currently, she serves as Customer Insights Specialist II at Reed Elsevier Shared Services, Inc. branch in Iloilo City.

Baleña's dedication to writing was evident early on when, as a high school sophomore, she clinched first place in a national essay writing contest jointly sponsored by the Philippine Veteran's Bank and the Inquirer. Since then, she has occasionally contributed essays to national and international publications. Her

academic achievements include being honored as both a College Scholar and a University Scholar at the University of the Philippines in the Visayas.

Beyond her academic and professional pursuits, Liliha Chelle finds solace and passion in her hobbies. She enjoys reading novels, playing the piano, sketching, and creating graphic designs during her leisure hours.

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Dedication

I take great pride and immense love in dedicating this work to the pillars of my life: my parents and my beloved brother, John Eddrex. Beyond the material sacrifices they made on my behalf, their uncompromising love and understanding have been the driving force that helped me conquer my worries and imbued me with the inspiration to strive for the best in times of my struggles.

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Moreover, this study has brought me profound religious enlightenment, making it fitting to dedicate this work to all Christians. I pray that it may serve as a source of inspiration, reminding us all to stand steadfast in our faith and to uphold the teachings of the Bible.

Ultimately, my eternal love and dedication are offered to the Divine Creator, who has been my unwavering source of strength and guidance.

With deep gratitude and love,

Liliha Chelle D. Baleña

Abstract

Within the broader context of the ASEAN, this study addressed the critical need for feedback on the gender equality (GE) movement by employing a combination of in-depth interviews and a survey approach to investigate the perspectives of 60 qualified Filipino respondents. The research focused on assessing the respondents' level of understanding, degrees of acceptance, concerns, and perceived benefits of the GE movement. Complementary interviews with gender experts and a thorough historical analysis of gender literature contributed to an understanding of the GE movement from a holistic perspective.

The study findings revealed that: (1) Respondents demonstrated substantial understanding of GE; (2) The GE movement was perceived as a potentially disruptive force in the society, particularly concerning its deviation from traditional beliefs, including religious practices; (3) The movement raised concerns that were particularly seen as disproportionate to its claimed beneficial impact; and (4) The movement absorbed big public funds without delivering tangible benefits.

From the results of the research, it is notable that the primary beneficiaries of the GE movement did not appear to be the affected population. Insights from interviews underscored a common source of ideas, suggesting a link to external influences. Interestingly, survey responses often contradicted the prevailing ideas aggressively promoted in the literature. Regrettably, however, these valuable, dissenting perspectives have either been ignored or not actively encouraged. This study highlighted the critical need for more comprehensive and inclusive dialogues about the GE movement, situated within the specific context of the oriental ASEAN region. It underscores the significance of considering diverse viewpoints to foster a

more nuanced understanding and meaningful evaluation of the implementation of GE within the region.

Keywords: Gender Equality, ASEAN context, dissenting perspectives, inclusive dialogues

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Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

This chapter introduces the research topic, the problem, and significance of the study. It consists of five sections: (1) Background of the Study, (2) Statement of the Problem, (3) Objectives of the Study, (4) Scope and Limitations, and (5) Significance of the Study.

Section 1 provides the context and overview of the subject and the importance of the research topic or the rationale for conducting this study.

Section 2 identifies the main problem that the study aimed to investigate and the importance of the investigation.

Section 3 states the research objectives aimed to be achieved by this study, which served as guide in the conduct of this study.

Section 4 defines the scope and coverage, or the research limitations, which mainly explains the adverse conditions concurrent with the conduct of the study.

Section 5 enumerates the potential contributions or benefits that could be derived from the findings of this study, plus the potential benefactors.

Background of the Study

Gender Equality (GE, hereon) is a relatively recent equality construct recreated from social roles rather than actual biological sexual differences (cf. Briceño, 2019). The concept purports that men and women must enjoy equal human rights, valued goods, opportunities, and resources, while allowing for opportunities and potential to contribute to and benefit from all aspects of the society (Ramšak, 2017; Madgavkar & Tonby, 2017; Women's Feature Service Philippine, Inc., 2011). It further asserts that women must represent and produce half of the world's potential because they

constitute about half of the world's population. This assertion is assumed as prerequisite to achieving peace, full human potential, productivity, economic growth, and sustainable development (UN, 2020a).

One major selling point of the concept is that, if women participate in the works done by men, an estimated \$28 trillion (26%) could be added to the global gross domestic product (GDP) by 2025, approximately the equivalent of the combined economies of the United States and China (Madgavkar & Tonby, 2017). It is particularly claimed that a small increase in Asian women participation alone, from 57.7% to 66.2% (i.e., 8.5%), could already result to 30% growth in per capita income of the region – and for one generation. Thus, for instance, ASEAN countries can produce \$1.2 trillion worth of GDP for their economy (i.e., 30% more) if they altogether act on GE. Moreover, even in a less ideal scenario, wherein the countries simply match the best-performing country in the region, it is projected that their combined economies can add about \$400 billion or 9% to the GDP (Briceño, 2019). Thus, overall, it is considered a gargantuan waste of resources and “social injustice” if gender inequality is not reduced in countries across Asia (Madgavkar & Tonby, 2017).

On the other hand, the optimistic projections remain unverified and there is actually a missing literature to substantiate them. To the contrary, in fact, experts simultaneously claim that Asian countries already fare well in terms of human development despite the economic, political and cultural diversity. ASEAN women are also said to already possess the favorable heritage of gender relations, resilience, and the pragmatism of their local societies (Andaya, 2021). The ASEAN Commission on the Promotion and Protection of the Rights of Women and Children (ACWC, 2016) further reported that the women, who comprise almost half of about 625 million people in the ASEAN region, already thrive as entrepreneurs of micro- and small-scale

industries, which define the backbone of ASEAN's economy. Moreover, women already occupy leadership positions in both public and private spheres, girls at par with boys in terms of access to education, and most young women attend universities. Indeed, except for Malaysia and Papua New Guinea (on UN observer's status), several ASEAN countries already made it to "Asia's 10 most gender-equal countries," particularly with the Philippines rated at the top (WEC, 2018). In fact, the Philippines further maintained its consecutive excellent ratings of being 7th, 9th, and 8th in the region (WEF, 2016, 2017, & 2018).

Notwithstanding, newly computed social, political, and economic indices continue to arise across ASEAN countries suggesting an imperfect GE in the region. Gaps amongst countries are said not to have closed in terms of e.g., advancing the rights and welfare of women and girls being constantly threatened by violence and discrimination. The poorest of women are still being claimed to have limited or no access to basic health and welfare care nor the required capital to drive them economically (ACWC, 2016; Setianto, 2020; Conley, 2020). Thus, while the Philippines already earned the distinction as the most gender equal country in Asia, the new indicators now demands that it is actually behind in specific areas like female labor force participation rate (LFPR) and women safety. The country's female LFPR of 46% is said to be the lowest in Southeast Asia. The country is also touted as the bottom of the safety list and is one of the most dangerous places for women in the Asia-Pacific (Setianto, 2020; Evlanova, 2019). Moreover, the World Bank's Women, Business and the Law (WBL) of 2021 added that the legal dimension of GE in the country has already regressed due to lack of reforms since 2019 (Laforga, 2021).

The implication of GE as an issue cannot be understated inasmuch as a big chunk of the national budget is being devoted to aggressive gender promotions. There

is the dire need to establish some facts as to the true value of the movement and validate claims due to its promotion. Unfortunately, there is no parity of information as ASEAN studies continue in its trajectory of proliferating along the lines suggested by relentless promotions (e.g., Hauser, 2017; Wulansari, 2013). The media and literature are literally flooded by the exclusive ideas of popular feminists, professionals, elites, non-profits, environmentalists, western advocates, and socialists-globalists – the same closed groups involved in the planning and influencing of global ratings (cf. WEF, 2016, 2017, & 2018; ACWC, 2016). Consequently, the GE campaign has proceeded unopposed, despite well-known inconsistencies and controversies it created. Amidst an imbalanced information, by 2014, GE was already successfully incorporated in the constitutions of 143 of 195 UN member nations (UN, 2020a & b). Particularly, in the Philippines, the mainstreaming of government agencies was enthusiastically enforced, with no less than the country's Commission on Higher Education and the Department of Education leading the infusion of certain controversial GE concepts in university curricula, research, and extension - down to the secondary and elementary levels. Ultimately, a General Appropriation Act was even passed to require at least 5% of local up to national budgets to realize the GE policies (Women's Feature Service Philippine, Inc., 2011; Gender Mainstreaming Committee, 2006; Congress of the Philippines, 2008 a & b & 2013), adding burden to the already huge yearly donations of the country to the UN, e.g., \$83M in 2019 (Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Trade of New Zealand, 2013). Therefore, to an unknown extent, the undebated GE advocacy, through gender mainstreaming, already sealed at least the fate of education in the country.

Statement of the Problem

Unfortunately, no country would be spared from the GE dictum because of tremendous support from the UN and its global network of collaborators. Yet, the fact remains that GE is not a resolved matter. The ASEAN is severely impacted considering its huge population, abundant resources, and its distinctly diverse Oriental beliefs and cultures. One may imagine the gravity of imposing on this region the Western GE concept, along with controversial aspects, GE appears oppressive besides being a very costly intervention. Religious persecution alone heavily impacts the ASEAN that is home to, among varied devotees, the third largest population of Christians in the world. Significantly, the bulk of this population comprises Filipinos who, by virtue of belonging to a devoutly Christian nation, can now be the focus of inquiry regarding the GE movement.

Indeed, intriguing questions have been begging for answers: In view of unverified claims, how can an expensive movement be truly beneficial? Why is it treated like an urgent national priority? Do Filipinos truly welcome western radical ideas that contradict their traditional beliefs and practices (cf. Newman, 2018b; Driessen, 2018; Ludwig, 2018; Websdale, 2016; Naylor, 2018)? How do Filipino Christians specifically react to gender extremism and anti-biblical promotions (e.g., Blanco, 2019; Cruz, 2021; Reyes, 2017; Denison, 2021; CBN News, 2020; Jones, 2018; Quintanilla, 2021; Ciccotta, 2018; Briceño, 2019)? Finally, for all the troubles, is GE even a real problem to begin with?

In all fairness, therefore, clouds of doubt surround the core of GE's credibility, and this needs serious investigation. The answers could not be found in promotional materials. Unfortunately, neither are they discussed in the literature, ironically, while a massive mound of gender materials has been forming (Chapter II). Therefore, the

recourse is to elicit opinions directly from the affected populations, i.e., through their crucial feedback. This will highlight the paramount importance of understanding the Oriental perspective of GE among Filipino respondents by immersing in their cultural prisms, local dynamics, traditional values, identities, and adaptive mechanisms. Through a qualitative inquiry and participant narratives, it would be possible to underscore the critical role of the present research in shedding light on a largely unexplored facet of gender GE within the Philippines and the larger Oriental region.

Practical limitations prompt the initial focus on Filipino participants. Nevertheless, this acknowledges that the Filipino perspective encapsulates the broader Oriental themes while recognizing that the limitations set the stage for potential future research involving a broader ASEAN population.

Objectives of the Study

In view of further restrictions (next section), the investigation narrowed down its purpose to involving a manageable group of participants known as Ilonggos, from Iloilo Province, in the central part of the Philippines. Despite this limitation, the research emphasized the prime significance of capturing participant perspectives, as no other existing or reliable sources of information adequately encompass the essence of the Oriental perspective on GE within the Filipino context.

The study thus aimed to achieve the straightforward objective of investigating the perceptions of a group of Ilonggos about GE, its claimed importance, and urgency, via the group's understanding, acceptance, concern, and appraisal of the benefit of the movement.

The following were the specific questions asked:

- a. What is the level of understanding of GE of the Ilonggos?

- b. What is the level of acceptance of GE of the Ilonggos?
- c. How concerned are the Ilonggos about GE?
- d. What are the perceived benefits of GE to the Ilonggos?

Scope and Limitations

Both the scope and coverage of this study were delimited in view of the difficulties encountered during the conception and conduct of the research.

First of all, the meager resources made it plausible to involve only 60 participants. For the same reason, it was deemed most practical to conduct the study in Iloilo being also the home province of the researcher. Getting extra assistance was greatly facilitated, and the researcher was naturally attuned to the Ilonggo culture.

Second, technically, the findings would reflect the thoughts of the Ilonggo group sampled and for the sampling period considered. It is crucial to consider, however, as typical in any ASEAN country, that anywhere in the Philippines, people are uniformly religious, and that, in fact, Filipinos constitute the majority of ASEAN Christians. Thus, within a regional context, the sample group would offer a fair characterization of the Oriental response to the Western GE imposition.

Third, any inter-comparison involving ASEAN countries was actually beyond the scope of this study. The same limitation applied to an involved discussion of social constructs, which are known to arbitrarily vary in complexity from one place to another and over time. Topics such as gender identities, roles, orientations, or preferences were complicated and controversial as they arose from discordant studies of feminist movements, which have frequently been described as chaotic, multivalent, and disconcerting (cf. Rampton 2019).

Fourth, there could not be any exhaustive search, much less the inventory, of the massive GE literature. The explosion of materials generated about the subject matter made data gathering and the ensuing analysis intractable (see Chapter II). Nevertheless, it is worth mentioning that the current literature search had logged far more references possible from modest academic research.

Fifth, not unlike other global advocacies, GE is host to unsettled issues. The more relevant allusions to Global Warming (GW hereon), a.k.a. Climate Change, the most popular UN-espoused advocacy, were kept to a minimum because voluminous materials have already been generated about the subject. Similarly, particular discussions about socio-political ideologies like socialism and communism were avoided.

Finally, the study truly pushed through under severe conditions. Data collection frequently stalled and was strictly regulated because of the COVID-19 pandemic. Most activities were confined online because personal meetings were not feasible. Travels and interactions were also restrained by stringent vaccination and quarantine testing policies.

Significance of the Study

The findings of this study have potential implications and benefits:

- a. Primarily, this study addresses a critical gap in the GE movement – its feedback. While this nation has been continually exposed to GE through numerous promotional materials, there has been a notable absence of information regarding the valuable public reactions. The current findings help clarify the unverified but persistent assertions popularized by gender theorists and globalists regarding the acceptance, benefits, importance, and urgency of GE.

- b. GE is undeniably controversial, and it would be unfair to assume its benefits without verifying public opinion, particularly in cases of potentially biased policies. In this context, this study promotes open-mindedness and critical thinking by facilitating a comprehensive discussion of contentious issues. It is essential to emphasize this need, given the historical susceptibility of Filipinos to foreign domination and potential exploitation.
- c. The findings shed light on the relentless and, oftentimes, intimidating nature of the GE propaganda driven by group-think ideologies. They underscore the necessity for active public involvement, and draw parallels to the lessons learned from the debunked GW fallacy, serving as both a lesson and an inspiration.
- d. The findings provide valuable insights into the financial, social, and religious impacts of GE on the Philippines, a developing ASEAN country. Notably, the extensive spending by concerned agencies, professionals, and nonprofits on GE-related activities has been largely overlooked.
- e. In a predominantly Christian nation, the findings highlight how the natural (divine) order is perceived to be violated by what seems to be an aggressive feminist ideology. This aspect has profound implications for personal, familial, and societal well-being.
- f. Any advocacy that lacks relevance or necessity can be detrimental, not only in terms of financial costs but also due to the spread of misinformation and the adverse reactions it generates. Current findings unveil the hitherto undisclosed consequences of imposing controversial GE ideas on the population.
- g. The findings offer insights into why GE and other global advocacies continue to proliferate, well-funded, despite the inconsistencies and undesirable controversies

that they create. This serves as a wake-up call to the population on revealing the true nature of global advocacies.

- h. Furthermore, the findings underscore the need to address and overcome weak and exploited Filipino values, which have historically facilitated the successful imposition of foreign influences across generations.
- i. Finally, the present findings emphasize the necessity for a scientific database that can support future comparative studies conducted in other localities within the ASEAN region. Such substantial scientific work is currently lacking, and it is crucial to understand how ASEAN cultures handle GE as a foreign imposition, especially in the context of the UN's broader plan for a one-world government (e.g., Matt, 2020). This realization is essential as every nation strives to preserve its identity and culture in the face of challenges posed by GE.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter reviews the relevant academic literature and related research studies about the global gender movement, down to its impacts to the ASEAN region, particularly, the Philippines. This is done in an attempt at identifying and focusing on the gaps that the present research aims to address. At the onset, it is worth emphasizing that, while gender-related publications have surged at a maximum rate of about 54% in only 20 months of this research, hardly any reference is available that mentions about criticisms of the GE advocacy or its actual impact to people, not to mention people's actual assessment of the advocacy. The internet is simply swarmed by GE promotional materials being rapidly produced by advocating entities.

The chapter is divided into six sections: (1) Sex and Gender, (2) GE and the ASEAN Scenario, (3) GE Impact in the Philippines, (4), Ominous Contradictions, (5) Inconvenient Revelations, and (6) A Summary.

Section 1 briefly reviews the crucial historical points in the evolution of sex, gender, and gender-fluid/LGBTI concepts that departed from well-rooted traditions. This establishes a theoretical foundation for this research.

Section 2 explores the GE concept and the nature of the global movement in the general context of the ASEAN situation.

Section 3 investigates the specific implementation and impact of GE policies in the Philippines. The section discusses the abrupt transformation of the nation in response to the GE imposition. It elaborates on the promotion mechanisms and the particularly successful gender mainstreaming that exemplifies the implantation of gender ideas worldwide.

Section 4 discusses the issues and contradictions about the GE implementation. Explained are the resulting controversies, particularly, the GE transgressions of tradition and the natural order. These relate to impositions done in the name of the feminist ideology, which conflict with the well-established patriarchal foundation of ASEAN religions and traditions, particularly Christianity.

Section 5 highlights the inconvenient findings or aspects of the GE movement. Discussed are some eye-openers about UN-sponsored advocacies, the activities of the nonprofit sector, and the collective bearing to the GE advocacy. This section specifically reveals the GW fallacy as the most contentious of the UN-espoused ideologies.

Section 6 provides a concise summary of the chapter, aiming to enhance the rationale of the study.

Sex and Gender

Since time immemorial, the world has understood the word *sex* or *gender* as interchangeable and always in the same context of male or female humans. Till recently, *sex* is defined accordingly as the set of biological attributes in humans and animals and primarily associated with physical and physiological features that include the chromosomes, gene expression, hormone levels and function, and reproductive or sexual anatomy. It is categorically either male or female, although there may be variations in biological attributes and how the attributes are expressed. Historically, *male* or *masculinity* also connotes attributes of strength, protection, independence, camaraderie, discipline, rivalry, militarism, aggression, savagery, and brutality; while *femininity* symbolizes weakness, fragility, helplessness, emotionality, passivity,

domestication, nurturance, attractiveness, partnership, excess, and temptation (Scott, 1986). This is within the natural order of things.

However, *gender* was abruptly divorced from its traditional binary (male-female) meaning. It was for the purpose of accommodating socially and even politically constructed roles (gender roles), behaviors, expressions, and identities involving girls, women, boys, men, and the so-called gender-diverse people. *Gender* was then presumed to reflect how people perceive themselves and each other, how they act and interact, and the distribution of power and resources in the society. As a result, beyond the binary conceptualization of girl-woman and boy-man, there is now an appreciable diversity in how individuals and groups understand, experience, and express the concept (cf. Canadian Institutes for Health Research, 2015; Women's Feature Service Philippine, Inc., 2011). In short, *gender* evolved into a complex and unfamiliar socio-psychological and psycho-analytic context. Further, as early as 1986, feminists have already referred to it as some social construction of sex differences, while theorists elevated it to a level akin to class or race (Scott, 1986). The new gender concept is still evolving but, notably, the crucial consequence already happened - its final departure from the biological binary concept (Rydstrøm, 2010).

Gender issues have since been lavishly espoused in public rallies, calling for recognition (accommodation or inclusion) of individual gender preferences, identities, or orientations. Further, and more unfortunately, these same events also inspired extremisms, particularly, the bizarre form of “gender fluid” ideas associated with the “social inclusion” struggle of LGBTIs. The situation resembled the early days of prostitution and sexual promiscuity described in the Bible (MacArthur, 1992 a & b; cf. Wilhelm, 2014). It is notable that LGBTI only began with homosexuality as inspired by a tiny population of lesbian women (MacArthur, 1981b). The “fluid” group has

remained very influential although they comprise only a minor sector of the global population, in the particular case of the Philippines, hardly 1% of the population (LAGABLAB, 2006). However, politicians spoil minority populations, and thus fuel their excessive and irrational demands, e.g., the banning of the “he/she” pronouns and the creation of 33 gender classes (Australia), hundreds more in America, all requiring the overhauling of existing laws (e.g., Mourad, 2018; Margan, 2018), the banning of the Bible to undermine Christianity (California) (Jones, 2018), and the introduction of gender-branding such as the “gay pride” and media “drag queens,” which continue to influence children’s values (e.g. Reyes, 2017; Denison, 2021). The general predicament is projected to worsen as gender-fluid activists target the ultimate annihilation of the Bible and Christianity (CBN News, 2020).

GE and the ASEAN Scenario

Social and feminist historian Prof. Martha Rampton explained that GE had ancient feminist roots - way back to Sappho of ancient Greece (c. 570 BC), Hildegard of Bingen of medieval times (1179), or Christine de Pisan (1434). The forerunners of modern movements included Olympe de Gouge (1791), Mary Wollstonecraft (1797), and Jane Austen (1817), whose advocacies mainly revolved around the concepts of dignity, intelligence, and the basic female potential. However, a series of clearly identifiable feminist movements began in the late 19th century: the First Wave (late 19th - early 20th century), which focused on suffrage; Second Wave (1960s-1990s) on sexuality and reproductive rights; Third Wave (began in mid-90s) on “universal womanhood,” globalism, and multiculturalism; and the Fourth Wave (emerging) on issues about sexual abuse, rape, violence against women, and unequal pay. History

also reveals GE as an old complex concept that has always been associated with a broad spectrum of disagreements and activism (Rampton 2019).

In principle, GE claims to promote equal accessibility to resources and opportunities that, regardless of gender, encompasses economic and decision-making opportunities and the valuing of behaviors, aspirations, and needs. The International Labor Organization (ILO, 2000 & 2014; Son, 2010) justifies this “equality” in that all humans are supposedly free to develop their abilities and make choices free from limitations set by stereotypes, rigid gender roles, and prejudices. Different behaviors, aspirations, and needs of men and women are said to be equally considered, valued, or favored. Further, while men and women are distinct, their rights, responsibilities, and opportunities are crucially independent of whether they are born male or female. “Gender equity” is the way of attainment, and it literally means fairness of treatment of men and women according to their respective needs. The treatment must be equivalent in terms of rights, benefits, obligations, and opportunities (cf. Son, 2010). In theory, GE is likewise said to represent an ideal condition that affords women and men equal enjoyment of human rights, socially valued goods, opportunities and resources, while allowing for both sexes the same opportunities and potential to contribute to and benefit from all spheres of the society - economic, political, social, and cultural (Ramšak, 2017; Madgavkar & Tonby, 2017; Women’s Feature Service Philippine, Inc., 2011).

In practice, however, GE has always espoused feminism. It has adopted a new gender construct that invokes social roles, abandoning the natural sexual differences, which were instead blamed – without concrete proof - for spawning inequality in many dimensions of everyday life. Indeed, by ending reference to the natural sexual dichotomy, with which individuals were born with, it was not far from strange to argue

that the new construct allows for men and women to equally possess the same rights, responsibilities, and opportunities. The new social construct instead better accommodates the varied interests, needs, and priorities of social or interest groups (Briceño, 2019).

Gender experts lately assert that women and girls must represent and produce half of the world's potential simply because they constitute about half of the world's population. This is further claimed to be a requirement for achieving peace, the full human potential, productivity, and sustainable economic growth and development (UN, 2020a). However, these assertions were solely based on correlating the global indices of the Gender Parity Score (GPS, based on 15 economic and social indicators of GE), which simply suggest that high-scoring countries had no low scores associated with work and the economy. Yet, globalists quickly exploited this, projecting that, if women were to participate in jobs normally suited for men, an additional \$28 trillion, or 26% of incremental global GDP, could be generated by 2025, i.e., an increase in assets roughly equal to the combined economies of the United States and China (Madgavkar & Tonby, 2017).

The ASEAN countries alone were projected to add \$1.2 trillion to the GDP of their economies (i.e., 30% more) if they act on gender inequality. Further, even in the barest scenario, wherein these countries simply match the progress of the currently best-performing country in the region, ASEAN economies could still acquire \$400 billion or an additional 9% for their GDPs. Briceño (2019) even claimed that just a small increase in Asian women's participation from 57.7% to 66.2% can already result in 30% growth in per capita income of the region - for one generation. As these projections suggested, it would then be a huge waste of resources or a "social injustice" if gender inequality remains high across Asia (Madgavkar & Tonby (2017).

Unfortunately, however, there are no other reliable sources that can either corroborate or refute the existence of this sort of economic problem in the region.

ASEAN is a region of at least 625 M people and, despite the region's economic, political and cultural diversities, the member countries are said to fare well in general measures of human development. Southeast Asian women may look forward to a promising future from their heritage of favorable gender relations and the resilience of local societies (Andaya, 2021). Still GE advocates insist that the region may only fulfill its full potential by including women in the push for more aggressive change since, again, almost half of the ASEAN population are women. Yet, women continue to thrive as entrepreneurs of both micro- and small-scale industries, the backbone of the ASEAN economy (Madgavkar & Tonby, 2017). Nowadays, women even occupy many leadership positions in both public and private spheres, girls at par with boys in terms of access to education, and most young women attend universities (ACWC, 2016). In fact, except for Malaysia and Papua New Guinea (UN 'observers'), several ASEAN countries already made it to "Asia's 10 most gender-equal countries," with the Philippines at the top (WEC, 2018). In particular, the Philippines successively placed 7th, 9th, and 8th in the region (WEF, 2016, 2017, & 2018).

Notwithstanding, newer indicators of social, political, and economic commonalities are continually being conceived to assert that GE is nowhere near perfect in the ASEAN. New gender "gaps" between countries have been defined concerning the rights and welfare of girls and women, now assumed to be under constant threats from violence and discrimination and, ironically, as a result of the "borderless society" and fast-paced advances in technology. The poorest of women (no mention of men) were described to have limited or no access to basic health and welfare care or the required capital to drive them economically (ACWC, 2016;

Setianto, 2020.) Thus, ironically, after just being crowned for being the most gender-equal nation in Asia, the new indices berated the Philippines as falling behind in new specifics like female labor force participation rate (LFPR) and women safety. The country was reassessed to have a female LFPR of 46% that was the lowest in Southeast Asia. In terms of women's safety, the country was likewise found at the bottom of the list and even touted as one of the most dangerous places for women anywhere in the Asia-Pacific (Setianto, 2020). Furthermore, the World Bank's Women, Business and the Law (WBL) 2021 reported a regression of the legal aspect of GE, particularly, about certain laws and regulations that restrict economic opportunity for women across 190 economies, as indicated by the lack of new reforms implemented since 2019 (Laforga, 2021). Ironically, again, these contradicted the fact that the country currently holds a large percentage of women in high-ranking positions - some 46.6% of senior management posts, which far exceeds even the global average of 24.14%.

Additionally, while rating the ASEAN countries in the middle of the global pack, the same GPS indices were used to show that their economies vary widely in terms of social mores and economics, i.e., far from the desired uniformity, a new problem. Economic development was said to enable countries to close gender gaps, but to accelerate progress, this has to occur in all four areas - education level, financial and digital inclusion, legal protection, and unpaid care work. Moreover, much was said to be done about legal provisions guaranteeing the rights of women as full members of the society and how such will improve the social indicators on violence against women, child marriage, unmet needs for family planning, and education. Again, this sounds odd as these same issues were also linked to an increase in labor-force participation among women (Madgavkar & Tonby, 2017; Laforga, 2021). On top of these demands,

the higher gender agenda perennially insists on solving the “three major global problems” - women’s leadership (politics), economic empowerment and skills development (job opportunity), and violence against women and girls (UN Women, 2018). Hence, there are constantly “remaining” issues in each of the 10 ASEAN countries - Philippines, Bangladesh, Mongolia, Lao PDR, Singapore, Vietnam, Thailand, Myanmar, Indonesia, and Cambodia (WEF, 2018). In the case of the Philippines, for now, there remain issues about wage equality and health survival.

As to how every advocated issue actually varies with time and country, and how the gaps between countries fare under every new set of assessment indices, remains tenuous. From a historical perspective, it appears unending. The GE dream of a utopian “Equiterra” is certainly sounding nice, but its realization appears like an evolving marvel of uncertainty (cf. Conley, 2020).

GE Impact in the Philippines

The global impact of GE campaigns has been massive, powerful, and thorough. The particular case of the Philippines may be viewed as one classic transformation, made possible by a very enthusiastic response to the implantation of a foreign ideas.

In retrospect, crucial to gender promotion was the creation of the United Nations (UN) in 1945, which in turn established the first Commission on the Status of Women. The UN has since been tasked to serve as venue for addressing transboundary issues that could not be resolved effectively by any country alone. The body orchestrated global discussions in time with the surge of feminist movements in the 70s. It held the First World Conference in 1975 (Mexico City), and put up the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) in 1979, which was regarded as the “International Bill of Rights for Women.” These events were

followed in 1985 by the Third World Review Conference (Nairobi), hailed as “the birth of global feminism” because it declared all human rights issues to be just women’s issues. The Fourth World Conference on Women in 1995 (Beijing) further pushed the controversial idea that women’s rights define “universal” human rights. In 2000, world leaders would gather in UN to “shape a broad vision to fight poverty in its many dimensions.” That vision translated into the eight Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) that also served as GE framework of 189 UN Member States for another 15 years (2000-2015). In particular, GE was the so-called MDG Target No. 3, and it was universally recognized as central to achieving the other seven targets. Also in 2000, the UN Security Council Resolution 1325 on Women, Peace, and Security spelled out the roles for men and women, highlighting the specific actions. Further, in 2003, the Optional Protocol was ratified and, along with CEDAW, it defined what constitutes discrimination against women, obligating all governments to take action to promote and protect women’s rights (Kabeer, 2005; cf. Inter-Agency and Expert Group on MDG Indicators, 2015). UN Women was further created in 2010 to achieve GE and women’s empowerment. In 2017, UN tied up with the European Union in launching Spotlight Initiative, a global initiative on eliminating all forms of violence against women and girls (UN, 2020a & b).

The global gender (for women) campaigns have been relentless. Recently, the UN Secretary-General declared that GE and the empowerment of women and girls are still the “unfinished business of our time,” urging continued promotion and funding (cf. UN, 2020a). The “unfinished business” was naturally parroted and echoed locally. The Declaration and Platform for Action produced by the 1995 Beijing conference was echoed within the framework of yet another domestic version of the plan, the 30-Year Philippine Plan for Gender Responsive Development (The PPGD 1995-2025), which

was accordingly signed on 08 September 1995 as Executive Order 273. Afterwards, the Framework Plan for Women was initiated in 1999 with the Medium-Term Philippine Development Plan (2001-2004) (Gender Mainstreaming Committee, 2006; Inter-Agency and Expert Group on MDG Indicators, 2015).

As products of globally coordinated movements, ASEAN gender studies flooded the literature as women groups, nonprofits, country representatives, environmentalists, and socialists-globalists toed the line set by global agreements and lauded by global assessments. The materials generated are by now too voluminous to quote: For instance, the keywords “gender,” “gender equality,” “gender equity,” “women empowerment,” and “feminism” produced literally billions of hits in a single online search. In the more local case of the Philippines, an online search made on 11 December 2018 (11:37 a.m.) yielded 12,700,000 for “gender equality in the Philippines,” 3,800,000 for “articles about gender equality in the Philippines,” and 30,700,000 for “current gender issues in the Philippines.” The corresponding updates on 10 August 2020 (10:36 p.m.) were 15,700,000, 5,850,000, and 42,000,000, indicating rates of increase of 24%, 54%, and 37%, respectively, i.e, in a matter of only about 20 months. Indeed, it is a voluminous accumulation of materials, yet, remarkably, critiques of or feedback on real issues could hardly be found.

Evidently, the surge of attention afforded to GE issues was horrendous. Unfortunately, this may not be construed as a validation of the soundness or acceptability of the GE concept. On the contrary, it is more widely perceived that the GE popularity is mainly the result of relentless campaigns fueled by the “money flood” that has lured countless professionals to global advocacies (Watts, 2010; Moore, 2018 a & b). The gargantuan financing likewise explains why a multitude of women and LGBTIs abruptly turned as gender advocates or feminists. Certainly, the proliferating

gender studies in the ASEAN were constantly encourage by global rankings (e.g., Hauser, 2017; Wulansari, 2013) apart from the old impasse concerning religion or tradition (e.g., Hirschman, 2016).

Since assessment indices are unpredictable, the gender gaps identified remain uncertain, and this ramps up the cost of pursuing the desired outcomes (cf. Conley, 2020). More unfortunately, reporting is unmindful of valid issues, for instance, the fact that ASEAN countries already view GE as a foreign imposition that threatens their national ideals (Stivens, 2010). Worst, it is by now glaring that the various assessment mechanisms and their indices do not factor in religion and freedom for all. This omission has had very serious consequences especially to Christian populations.

GE is also inherently an incompatible foreign ideology for ASEAN countries. Its western-style promotional bias is an irony for an equality movement because it produces incontrovertible ideologies in favor of influential elites. In fact, by 2014, the apparent lack of public participation or opposition already made possible the incorporation of the GE ideology in the constitutions of 143 of 195 UN nations (De Vera-Ruiz, 2017; UN, 2020a & b).

In the Philippines, the overpowering GE agenda immediately forced the fast-paced mainstreaming of all government agencies and institutions, with no less than the country's Commission on Higher Education and the Department of Education leading the infusion of controversial gender concepts in university curricula, research, and extension – all down to the secondary and elementary levels. Equally remarkable, the General Appropriation Act was swiftly passed, requiring for at least 5% of local to national budgets to fund the realization of GE laws and policies (Women's Feature Service Philippine, Inc., 2011; Gender Mainstreaming Committee, 2006; Congress of the Philippines, 2008 a & b & 2013). This substantial money allocation was on top of

the already huge yearly donation of the Philippines (\$83.0M in 2019) to the umbrella organization of the promotion - the UN (Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Trade of New Zealand, 2013.) As a matter of quick accounting, at current exchange rate of ₱58 to \$1, one yearly donation is sufficient to run 12 to 15 local universities for a year. Indeed, it is further curious that the country makes a comparable contribution to Australia (UN, 2021), which is a far wealthier nation. Just how local and national agencies and institutions actually justify the spending of their respective budgets could well be another interesting subject of research.

To further ensure an effective national GE mainstreaming, the Joint Circular 2012-01 by the Philippine Commission on Women (PCW, formerly NCRFW), National Economic and Development Authority (NEDA), and the Department of Budget and Management (DBM) issued the Guidelines for the Preparation of Annual Gender and Development (GAD) Plans and Budgets and Accomplishment Reports to Implement the Magna Carta of Women. The recipients were all heads of executive departments, agencies, bureaus, offices, state universities and colleges, government owned and/or controlled corporations (GOCCs), legislative and judiciary branches, constitutional bodies, other government instrumentalities, and all other concerned entities (Women's Feature Service Philippine, Inc., 2011; Gender Mainstreaming Committee, 2006). The involvement of the budget department (DBM) in the whole process sealed the nation's commitment to finance the western feminist movement. Notably, the widespread and pervasive government enforcement of the GE ideology, dragged along the learning institutions, guaranteeing a truly gender-biased education for Filipinos (cf. Lukas, 2019; Ladrido, 2018; Sallave, 2014).

Finally, gender mainstreaming in the Philippines was truly one massive undertaking, practically involving all the crucial agencies of the government. Further,

they jointly concerted to the pivotal use of the media/communication network to form a comprehensive control system, charging separate agencies with particular tasks of advancing women's interests in the country: The PCW, in coordination with relevant agencies and media organizations, formulates media guidelines to protect women against discrimination in the media and film. The Office of the Press Secretary (OPS) and its attached agencies ensure the formulation of policies and implementation of programs pursuant to the RA 9710, to include the over-all direction, guidance and monitoring being the lead agency of government mass media, formulation and implementation of a national communication plan and advocacy activities, plus the creation of a Gender Equality Committee comprising of representatives from the OPS, PCW, various self-regulatory bodies and the National Telecommunications Commission (NTC), Movie and Television Review and Classification Board (MTRCB), Film Academy of the Philippines (FAP), Film Development Council of the Philippines (FDCP), Optical Media Board (OMB), National Commission for Culture and the Arts (NCCA), and representatives of women's media NGOs.

Meanwhile, the pillars of the country's educational system, the Department of Education (DepEd), Commission on Higher Education (CHED), and the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) were charged with developing and promoting the gender-sensitive curricula, "gender-fair" instructional materials and capacity-building programs on gender, peace and human rights education for their officials, faculty, and non-teaching staff and personnel, promotion of educational partnerships, provision of free use of space for campaigns against women's discrimination and violence, and guaranteed scholarships to marginalized women regardless of age, pregnancy, motherhood, disabilities, or lack of consent of husband. The NTC, MTRCB, FAP, FDCP, OMB, NCCA were to ensure that the communication

industries - media and film - comply with the Act and, among others, the formulation of policies and programs for raising the consciousness of the general public about recognizing women's dignity and their roles and contribution in all spheres of private and public life, allocation of space, airtime, and resources for the airing of advertisements of women's human rights, gender-based trainings, and the integration. Overall, the PCW would act as the primary policy-making and coordinating body of women and GE concerns, directly under the Office of the President. While, the Commission on Human Rights (CHR) would undertake the compliance of PCW and other agencies, the imposition of penalties, and the creation of its Women's Human Rights Center (e.g., Women's Feature Service Philippine, Inc., 2011; Gender Mainstreaming Committee, 2006).

In sum, suffice it to say, that the unopposed, lopsided, and lavish push for women's welfare in all of the media and agencies cemented the equivalence of GE and feminism in the Philippines (cf. Lukas, 2019; Ladrido, 2018; Sallave, 2014).

Ominous Contradictions

The assertion that GE is beneficial, thus needing an urgent societal solution, is wrought with contradictions and controversies (Lukas, 2019; Ladrido, 2018; Sallave, 2014). This section explains some important contradictions surrounding the GE discourse. These contradictions are evident with the aggressive promotions, misrepresentation of historical and religious contexts, and especially as challenges to deeply held cultural values in predominantly Christian ASEAN countries like the Philippines. These contradictions underscore the complexity of the issue and its far-reaching implications.

Inequitable Promotion and Misrepresentation. Contradictions arise within the GE movement as it purports to combat gender bias while consistently promoting feminism (Lukas, 2019; Ladrido, 2018; Sallave, 2014). The movement popularizes the same talking points that portray women as disadvantaged minorities, akin to senior citizens, persons with disabilities (PWDs), cultural tribes, children, the poor, or the oppressed. Yet, even real instances such as suffrage suppression are usually isolated and culture-related (Wallstrom, 2018). Regrettably, the biased mode of promotion has led to influential policies favoring women, often at the expense of men, who are depicted as culprits or aggressors (UN Women, 2018; Sallave, 2014; De Vera-Ruiz, 2017; Gender Mainstreaming Committee, 2006). Moreover, the society's increasing tolerance to gender fluidity, such as the LGBTIs (CBN News, 2020), adds to the contradictions.

Historical and Religious Context. The roots of these contradictions extend back hundreds, and even thousands of years. From feminist Christine de Pizan (c. 1405) to the Shakers (1774-1788) in northwest England and beyond, tensions regarding gender roles and norms have persisted. Meanwhile, the Holy Bible has prescribed strict norms governing the conduct of men and women, emphasizing natural gender roles and capabilities (MacArthur, 1999 a & b). Nonbiblical interpretations or redefinitions of gender concepts are considered unnatural perversions by Christians (MacArthur, 1992 a & b; Ciccotta, 2018; Newman, 2016).

Misrepresentation of Patriarchy. Contrary to the narratives that confront historical patriarchy (PGR-KI, 2014; cf. Setianto, 2020; Hirschman, 2016; ACWC, 2016; Blanco, 2019; Jones, 2018; Reyes, 2017; CBN News, 2020; Quintanilla, 2021;), it can be argued that the persecution of patriarchy is a deliberate misinterpretation of the Scriptures. The Bible portrays men and women in terms of their natural roles and

capabilities (MacArthur, 1999 a & b, 2007; 1 Corinthians 11, 1 Peter 2). It emphasizes that men are providers and protectors of their families, explaining their leadership authority. However, it also highlights the significance of women, who complement men's deficiencies (Genesis 4; Richards, 1998). Women like Rebekah, Deborah, and Ruth were given special roles as rulers. Further accounts about Ester, Deborah, Tamar, Rahab, Ruth, Bethesda, and, prominently, the preferential worship time afforded to Mary (mother of Christ), clearly demonstrate the Bible's gender impartiality (Books of Judges and Luke; Matthew, 1:3).

Ideological Conflict. The fundamental ideological conflict arising from the GE movement had become apparent. It presents a choice between adhering to God's established concepts of gender identity, roles, and equity or embracing GE, which is viewed by many as an unnatural and ill-defined egalitarianism promoted by feminists, LGBTI, psychoanalysts, nonprofits, environmentalists, and global activist groups (MacArthur, 1981 a & b; 1992 a & b; Jones, 2018; O'Hare, 2012; Wise & Russell, 2018; Ciccotta, 2018; Matt, 2020).

Religious Suppression. GE's compatibility with LGBTI viewpoints has led to concerns that religious beliefs, particularly Christianity, are under siege. The movement's alignment with groups that seek to rewrite the Bible and diminish the influence of religions like Christianity raises troubling issues, given the substantial Christian population in the ASEAN (Jones, 2018; Reyes, 2017; CBN News, 2020; Quintanilla, 2021; Mourad, 2018; Margan, 2018; CBN News, 2020; The World Factbook, 2021). Regrettably, developments have occurred devoid of democratic consultations with the affected populations (De Vera-Ruiz, 2017).

Religious Implications. Being predominantly Christian, the Philippines faces unique problems with regards the GE movement (e.g., Buan, 2018 a & b). The

movement's impact on Filipino Christians cannot be understated, especially considering its far-reaching implications in the ASEAN region. For one, some 86M of the 131M ASEAN Christians are Filipinos (The World Factbook, 2021). This fact raises serious questions about the urgency and priority of GE in such a religiously diverse regional setting.

Impact on ASEAN Traditions. The GE movement has likewise generated controversies by challenging established ASEAN values and traditions. It is perceived by some ASEAN countries as a foreign imposition undermining their national ideals (Stivens, 2010). Assessment indices used by GE advocates are criticized for being arbitrary and unpredictable, and they often fail to consider religion and individual freedom (WEF, 2018; UN Women, 2018). The movement is further viewed as persecuting well-rooted patriarchal traditions and religions in the ASEAN region (PGR-KI, 2014; Andaya, 2021; Setianto, 2020; Hirschman, 2016; ACWC, 2016).

Public Opinion and ASEAN Values. In ASEAN countries of rich traditions, public opinion becomes crucial in evaluating the claims of the GE promotion. The clash between feminism, gender fluidity, and radical concepts, and the long-held ASEAN values is inevitable. Issues like "social inclusion" by the LGBTIs have been likened to biblical accounts of prostitution and promiscuity (MacArthur, 1992 a & b; Wilhelm, 2014). Emerging concerns including the Bible ban, pronoun changes, creation of multiple gender classes, and more, challenge deeply ingrained values and beliefs (Jones, 2018; Blanco, 2019; Mourad, 2018; Margan, 2018; Reyes, 2017; Denison, 2021; Cruz, 2021; Riddell, 2016; Evon, 2016; Lindsey & Sarri, 1992; Feeney, Christensen, & Moravcik, 2006; Elicay, 2021; CBN News, 2020). Apparently, the ultimate ideological conflict lies between the Bible and UN Agenda 21, obscured only by intense propaganda.

Inconvenient Revelations

Agenda 21, the blueprint of global advocacies was agreed upon in 1992 in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil by 193 UN member states. Pages of the agenda were peppered with feminist concerns as GE was construed as an urgent responsibility of every state. The proponents were prominent socialists and communists, who championed the “green” ideology (environmentalism) as a front act (Beck, 2011; Delingpole, 2011). A brief background of the much bigger GW advocacy and the nonprofits may lead to some crucial revelations.

Fortunately, GW, the biggest of the UN-espoused advocacies, already sparked a widespread awakening to the unscientific nature of global advocacies. The exposé began as the “Climategate” of 2009 (Sussman, 2010) and peaked in 2017 with US President Trump’s rejection of GW as a “hoax” (Melloan, 2018). Successive expositions caused the GW movement to lose scientific credibility (e.g., Taylor, 2015).

The underlying motive behind GW was finally made public during the 2018 UN COP24 event in Katowice, Poland, by Al Gore, an influential globalist, who revealed his bizarre “climate solution” (Newman, 2018b):

“... more restrictions on liberty and energy, more globalism, more extreme population-control measures, and a lower standard of living for people everywhere ... surrendering more money and power to the UN and governments under the guise of regulating CO₂ would somehow make the climate stop changing so everyone could live in peace and security.”

Socialists, communists, and globalists resounded with “exploit alarmism ... restructure every aspect of human life ... the economy, industry, governance, and even individual thinking.” In closing, UN Secretary-General Antonio Guterres urged everyone to believe that climate action is the “compelling path to transform our world” and the

“mind.” The messages confirmed the communistic grand plan for total world domination (Driessen, 2018; Ludwig, 2018) - nothing was scientific, and nothing was for science. Akin to a watermelon, everything was a charade of green on the outside but red intentions on the inside (Delingpole, 2011). [Underscoring supplied.]

GW has reigned as the greatest fallacy of saving humanity from imaginary or natural climate disasters, all falsely blamed on human activities (e.g., Michaels, 2007; Weart, 2003). The strategy was simplistic: Blame natural weather and climate changes on humans, being their destructive acts on the environment, and then offer communism as the solution. The GW advocacy is coercive and constantly calls for humanity to initiate “climate action,” which basically boils down to the solicitation of funds for building a state-controlled global government (e.g., Delingpole, 2011; Matt, 2020; Durden, 2018; Ludwig, 2018). Actual spending has been horrendous: \$1.5 trillion per year for decades, totaling \$42 trillion for every imagined (nonexistent) successful degree Fahrenheit lowering of global temperature, which has never been verified (Wrightstone, 2018; Lomborg, 2016). A renowned UC-Berkeley physicist, Dr. Hal Lewis, alluded to a global “money flood” that has engaged multitudes of professionals to the imaginary cause (Watts, 2010; Moore, 2018 a & b; Driessen, 2018). Websdale (2016) sums it all up: “One of the greatest swindles on the road to tyranny is ‘global warming’ or ‘climate change’.” Moore (2018b) further elaborated on the tremendous spending: He referred to a Climate Policy Initiative (CPI) study that found the global investment in climate change to have reached \$359 billion in 2013. Remarkably, this was still considered short of the group’s expectation of \$5 trillion - an amount that could feed the entire planet, provide clean water and electricity to far-flung corners of Africa, end malaria, and leave enough to find a cure for cancer and Alzheimer’s disease. By another comparison, the entire Apollo moon program cost

less than \$200 billion, while the world spends at least twice that amount on a virtual climate change problem – every year. Thus “money flood” appears an understatement (Watts, 2010; Moore, 2018 a & b).

The UN remains the largest nonprofit beneficiary of yearly donations from almost 200 member states. It has a yearly budget of about \$5.4B, and maintaining its global offices alone requires tens of millions of dollars (Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Trade of New Zealand, 2013). Unfortunately, while it constantly meddles with nations, it has not successfully carried out its own mandate since its creation (24 October 1945). Instead, the organization has addressed extra issues requiring more funding, e.g., GW, GE, human trafficking, drugs, terrorism, corruption, crimes and abuses, drugs, poverty, human rights violations, inequality, etc. Worse, it has unveiled a socialist plan of setting up a global government (e.g., O'Connor, 2018; Shaw, 2018; Burroughs, 2015; Simpson, 2008; Websdale, 2016; Newman, 2016 & 2018 a & b, Moore, 2018 a & b; Taheri, 2003; Tilt, 2005; Yamin, 2018; White & Hook, 2020). Remarkably, however, it holds on to and pursues its plans despite widespread criticisms (e.g., Melloan, 2018; Wrightstone, 2018; Bastasch, 2018; Sussman, 2010; Delingpole, 2018; Newman, 2018b; Goreham, 2018; White & Hook, 2020). It has already involved a religious figure, the Pope, in its global politics (e.g., Williams, 2018). Consequently, issues have emerged about its spending and performance (e.g., White & Hook, 2020). Recently, the body further exposed its internal woes by soliciting more cash, on top of the existing contributions (e.g., World Press Trust of India, 2018; White & Hook, 2020). As indication of eroded confidence, President Trump has initiated withdrawal of all US pledges that included the yearly donation of \$1.2B, a hefty 22% of the UN yearly budget. The move has reverberated to other countries (Volcovici,

2017; Zhang, Qing-Chen, Qiu-Hong, & Huang, 2017; Bastasch, 2018; Goreham, 2018; Delingpole, 2018).

The UN may have outlived its usefulness when it began working outside of its mandate (cf. Roberts, 2020; Burroughs, 2015; Simpson, 2008; Taheri, 2003; Melloan, 2018; Newman, 2018a; Ludwig, 2018; O'Connor, 2018; Shaw, 2018). Its particular patronage of GW created the costliest advocacy of all time, lasting decades of expended trillions only to forestall an imaginary runaway warming (Wrightstone, 2018; Lomborg, 2016; Melloan, 2018; Driessen, 2018). Yet, GW is believed to be just the major front of the planned One World Government of 2030 (Ludwig, 2018; Newman, 2018a; Shaw, 2018; Matt, 2020; McKinstry, 2016). The grand plan has the open support of leaders like Merkel (Germany) and Macron (France), who relentlessly campaign for nations to give up their sovereignties to a New World Order, even to the extent of ignoring domestic problems like national borders, immigration, and fiscal resources (Durden, 2018).

Have global ideologies brought in real benefits? This is crucial to ask, considering that poor nations are especially obliged to accommodate international dictates at their own expense. Unfortunately, the answer remains unknown and has never become any point of interest. Meanwhile, the nonprofit world has also turned worrisome, and this deserves some mention (e.g., Tilt, 2005).

Nonprofits have quickly transformed into the fastest-growing industry, controlling assets in excess of a trillion dollars (Hawks, 1997). Yet, many of them have been criticized as unqualified influencers (ADB, 2007; Edwards, 1998; Gomez, 1999; Fortes, 2000; Riedmiller, 2000; Wiener, 2000). Their free-form self-regulation is not scrutinized, which renders them prone to abuse (ADB, 1999; Kandy, 1997; Runyan, 1999). Moreover, there has been an absence of accounting and accountability (cf. Tilt,

2005). Thus, while Dr. Lewis alluded to the global circulation of trillions of dollars as the “money flood” (Watts, 2010), Hawks (1997) summed up nonprofit work as “Doing good is now good business.”

There is no parallel documentation about nonprofit activities in the ASEAN although, in the Philippines, a pork barrel scandal involving lawmakers, executives, and bogus NGOs was ominous for Filipinos (e.g., Mangahas, 2012). Some 500,000 nonprofits in the country vastly outnumber the country’s 42,028 barangays, yet hardly 1% of them are development-oriented (ADB, 1999, 2007; NSCB, 2014). Most of them adopt, advocate, fund, or are linked to controversial issues such as GE and GW. Unfortunately for this country, the laws on environmentalism, GW, and GE were already in place. Hence, further critical exposés may be hard to expect (cf. Congress of the Philippines, 2008 a & b, 2009, & 2013).

Not unlike GW and other advocacies, GE’s impositions on weak nations do speak for themselves. The gender movement has waded successfully through controversies, and it prevailed devoid of definitive accomplishments (e.g., Bjørnholt, 2014; Anonuevo, 2014; Santiago, 2008; Scott, 1986; ILO, 2014). The endpoint of the movement is unclear, but excuses abound in justifying its continued funding (cf. Inter-Agency and Expert Group on MDG Indicators, 2015; Conley, 2020). Unfortunately, costly as the global advocacies may be, it remains uncertain when the tasks of Agenda 21 will be completed (cf. Taheri, 2003). Already, plans for the New World Order are brewing with the forthcoming Agenda 30 and Agenda 50 (Brooker, 2020; Ice Age Farmer, 2021).

A Summary

The feminist roots of GE date back to around 570 BC, making it a longstanding concept. However, GE has evolved entangled in a spectrum of conflicts (Rampton, 2019). A pivotal moment occurred in the mid-80s when the traditional binary definition of gender was intentionally divorced from its biological aspects (Scott, 1986; Rydstrøm, 2010). This opened a floodgate of rapid expansion of gender concepts, challenging well-established traditions. Critics argue that the trend aimed to ultimately undermine these traditions (MacArthur, 1981b, 1992 a & b; Reyes, 2017; Mourad, 2018; Jones, 2018; Blanco, 2019; CBN News, 2020; Denison, 2021).

The redefinition of gender as a social construct aligned well with the goals of women's groups (Briceño, 2019). Advocates asserted that empowering women, who make up about half of the global population, would boost economic gains, as projected for the ASEAN economy (Madgavkar & Tonby, 2017). However, ASEAN countries already scored well in human development and GE (Andaya, 2021; ACWC, 2016; cf. WEF, 2016, 2017, & 2018), prompting the need for new indices to justify ongoing demands (cf. ACWC, 2016; Setianto, 2020; Laforga, 2021; Madgavkar & Tonby, 2017). These demands added to the already existing requirements set by the UN which, despite relentless promotions, were already widely perceived as fostering uncertainty for lacking concrete achievements (UN Women, 2018; cf. Conley, 2020).

The global impact of GE campaigns has been powerful and thorough because of the influence of the UN and its globally extensive network. Decades of collaboration resulted in conventions, protocols, concepts, and policies that immediately impacted countries worldwide (Kabeer, 2005; cf. Inter-Agency and Expert Group on MDG Indicators, 2015; UN, 2020a & b, 2021). Although the widespread impact was not necessarily a validation of acceptability, in fact, GE has garnered overwhelming

attention. A global “money flood” has fueled the movement, lured countless professionals, and converted women and LGBTIs into advocates (cf. Watts, 2010; Moore, 2018 a & b; Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Trade of New Zealand, 2013). ASEAN gender studies surged, constantly encouraged by global rankings (e.g., Hauser, 2017; Wulansari, 2013). Among the ASEAN nations, the Philippines stands out for its enthusiastic adoption of the foreign ideas, particularly incorporating gender policies into its Constitution, mainstreaming them across agencies, and mandating these agencies to allot funds for policy support (Gender Mainstreaming Committee, 2006; Inter-Agency and Expert Group on MDG Indicators, 2015; Women's Feature Service Philippine, Inc., 2011; Congress of the Philippines, 2008 a & b & 2013). Further, to ensure effective gender mainstreaming, key government bodies collaborated with influential media outlets and shape a specially gender-biased education (cf. Lukas, 2019; Ladrido, 2018; Sallave, 2014).

Yet, the claims that GE is a pressing concern have faced serious criticism. The movement is marred by contradictions and controversies involving feminist stances, the pursuit of minority status by women (Lukas, 2019; Ladrido, 2018; Sallave, 2014), tolerance of gender fluidity (CBN News, 2020; MacArthur, 1992 a & b; cf. Wilhelm, 2014), and alarming challenges to societal norms (e.g., MacArthur, 1981 a & b; 1992 a & b; Jones, 2018; O'Hare, 2012; Wise & Russel, 2018; Ciccotta, 2018; Matt, 2020). Significantly, serious conflicts arise over incompatibility with biblical teachings and the persistent persecution of patriarchy (e.g., MacArthur, 1992 a & b; 1999 a & b; Ciccotta, 2018; Newman, 2016; PGR-KI, 2014; cf. Setianto, 2020; Blanco, 2019). The main conflict revolves around opposing ideologies regarding gender identity, roles, and equity. One side aligns with a traditional, just, and natural perspective rooted in religious beliefs, while the other side advocates for an egalitarian approach supported

by groups like feminists, LGBTIs, psychoanalysts, nonprofits, environmentalists, and global activists. Despite being the minority, these groups aggressively seek revamp of established norms, including religious texts like the Bible (e.g., MacArthur, 1981 a & b; 1992 a & b; Jones, 2018; O'Hare, 2012; Wise & Russel, 2018; Ciccotta, 2018; Matt, 2020).

The GE movement faced bigger problems regarding the GW controversy, revealing the misleading nature of global advocacies (Beck, 2011; Delingpole, 2011). As awareness grew in that issues were being exploited for broader agendas, credibility suffered (Sussman, 2010; Melloan, 2018; Newman, 2018b; Driessen, 2018; Ludwig, 2018; cf. Delingpole, 2011; Durden, 2018; Matt, 2020). GW was debunked, revealed as a fundraising device, and now serious doubts are consequently cast on GE's credibility (e.g., Michaels, 2007; Weart, 2003; Wrightstone, 2018; Lomborg, 2016; Watts, 2010; Moore, 2018 a & b; Driessen, 2018; Websdale, 2016.)

In the ASEAN context, the clash between progressive oriental culture and western radical ideas, which particularly impact religion especially Christianity, is most pronounced, exacerbated by the fact that the ASEAN Christian population is the third largest in the world, and of which 70% being pious Filipinos. Given the cultural nuances, the opposition to ingrained beliefs and values spawns pressing problems exacerbated by a biased literature (MacArthur, 1992 a & b; Wilhelm, 2014; Jones, 2018; Mourad, 2018; Margan, 2018; Reyes, 2017; Denison, 2021; Blanco, 2019; CBN News, 2020). Remarkably, indeed, despite the wealth of gender materials, hardly a miniscule offer any balanced assessment or public opinion as basis, relying instead on unreliable reports and indices (cf. Conley, 2020). In particular, global reports often disregard local perspectives and the impact on religious freedom (Stivens, 2010).

Therefore, the implications of the GE movement are very significant and repressive, particularly for Christians, especially within the ASEAN context. Apparently, the movement proceeds with its global impact despite an atmosphere of criticisms, controversies, reduced credibility as a consequence of the debunked GW advocacy, conflict of ideologies, and the major clash between progressive oriental culture and Western radical ideas that particularly impact Christianity in the ASEAN region. Given a vast body of literature, still there is a lack of balanced assessments and conversations regarding the consequences of GE on affected populations, a predicament that urges a need for direct conversations with the affected taxpayers.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

This chapter expounds on the methodology using three sections: (1) Conceptual Framework, (2) Research Design, and (3) Research Procedures.

Section 1 frames the theory, the rationale to which this study was anchored. The section explains the conceptual framework that supports the study objectives, the paradigm that relates the identified research variables, the modeling of these variables, and it concludes with the study hypotheses. The paradigm served as basis for formulating the study hypotheses as it framed the theoretical rationale guiding the research.

Section 2 explains the appropriate research design for the study. Outlined are the general methodological plan and the requirements followed to accomplish the study objectives. Subsequently discussed are the specification of the participants, the inclusion-exclusion criteria of selection, and the configuration of the survey instrument.

Section 3 outlines the procedures followed by the research in an effort to ensure its optimal quality. Described in this section are the flow of procedures employed to produce the analyses, beginning with the meticulous collection of data, data processing and protocols, to the deployment of more sophisticated quantitative techniques to establish instrument reliability and validity.

In the subsequent chapters, the research outcomes are presented and contextualized in consonance with the methodological scaffold in order to provide rigor to the treatment of the results of this study.

Conceptual Framework

Introduction

GE is a controversial global issue that impacts the various aspects of the society and its development. Diverse regions and cultures often interpret and treat the issue differently. This study embarked on exploring the distinct Oriental perspective on gender and equality among Filipino respondents within the broader context of ASEAN countries.

While GE may have been intended to be universally applicable, a gap in the existing literature did exist concerning how ASEAN nations would perceive and approach GE within the context of their own shared cultural heritage and localized dynamics. A remarkably scant or irrelevant literature could not address this subject, hence prompting the present study to adopt a unique theoretical framework designed to directly engage the participants and their narratives. In particular, through an examination of Filipino viewpoints within this framework, the study aimed at unveiling the authentic understanding, negotiation, and acceptability of GE across the various cultural contexts, thereby enriching the global discourse on the subject.

Given the dearth of pertinent prior studies, particularly within the scope of the ASEAN countries, the formulation of a distinct theoretical framework was crucial. Acknowledging the limitations of the available literature, this framework would have to underscore the significance of engaging participants directly to effectively address the research objectives. It would have to amalgamate several fundamental ideas that cumulatively contribute to a more profound comprehension of GE in the ASEAN region, as follows:

First, the Oriental GE perspective among Filipino respondents is shaped by a mosaic of cultures spanning the ASEAN countries. These shared attributes, or

commonalities, encompass historical legacies, traditional beliefs, and societal norms that collectively mold gender perceptions and expectations. Motivated by the scarcity of relevant literature, the framework delves into how the shared attributes interact with the evolving gender perspectives.

Second, to bridge the research gap, a new understanding of GE necessitates an exploration of the intricate interplay between local dynamics and cultural nuances prevalent among ASEAN nations. The interweaving of indigenous values, historical trajectories, and societal hierarchies is instrumental in shaping responses to globalized gender norms.

Third, leveraging this research's originality, the framework ventures into the fusion of GE with individual and collective identities within the broader ASEAN context. This exploration examines how respondents perceive their identities within the framework of gender roles and equality, profoundly influenced by a shared cultural heritage.

Therefore, the study framework scrutinized how cultural norms adapt across ASEAN nations in response to the global concepts of GE, probing how participants may strike any balance between preserving cultural heritage and embracing progressive gender ideals to create a regional perspective. But due to the paucity of relevant prior research, the framework underscored the pivotal role of qualitative inquiry. It emphasized the central role of participant narratives and experiences in revealing insights, thereby offering a unique window into the ASEAN perspective on GE. The present study's practical limitations prompted an initial focus on Filipino participants. Simultaneously, however, it acknowledged that the Filipino perspective encapsulated broader ASEAN themes, while laying out the foundation for potential future research encompassing a wider ASEAN population.

Background of Research Gap

GW and GE. The debunking of the GW theory has unearthed profound insights into the global mobilization of vast financial resources (in trillions of dollars) to bolster misleading advocacies that mask the underlying agenda of globalization, primarily centered around achieving global supremacy (e.g., Michaels, 2007; Weart, 2003; Websdale, 2016; Matt, 2020; Newman, 2018b; Driessen, 2018; Ludwig, 2018). The dominant GW advocacy has endured largely unopposed due to its extensive network of non-profit organizations, collaborative agencies, institutions, and professionals, amply funded by a global "monetary deluge" (Hawks, 1997; Moore, 2018a & b; Driessen, 2018; Watts, 2010; Moore, 2018a & b). The global outreach has surged onward unabated, dismissing valid criticisms (Melloan, 2018; Wrightstone, 2018; Bastasch, 2018; Sussman, 2010; Delingpole, 2018; Newman, 2018b; Goreham, 2018; Durden, 2018; Ludwig, 2018; White & Hook, 2020).

Similarly, GE, a distinct feminist ideology within the same UN agenda, has also infiltrated the Constitutions of member nations (Gender Mainstreaming Committee, 2006) and, akin to GW, it has emerged as another point of widespread contention. Particularly, informed Filipinos recognize that GE should not be a national concern (cf. De Vera-Ruiz, 2017). For one, the original Constitution was inherently unbiased regarding gender matters. Furthermore, the notion of preferentially treating women as a minority group in the name of equality has also been debunked (cf. Conley, 2020).

The significance and urgency of GE are being amplified through propaganda. In reality, modern societies no longer resist GE due to the freedom individuals have had since the 20th century to engage in public life across a spectrum of social roles (cf. Brundage, 1991). Moreover, GE strategists have already evaluated 10 ASEAN countries highly on the gender parity index, with the Philippines consistently claiming

the top position (WEF, 2016, 2017, & 2018). In fact, ASEAN nations have little to gain from a Western ideology that conflicts with their Eastern values and traditions (e.g., Salaverria, Lim, Nawal, & Alipala, 2018). Besides, hosting international programs strains their resources and impedes progress. For instance, the annual contributions of ASEAN countries to the UN are substantial, and the Philippines alone donates approximately \$83 million in addition to 5% of its annual budget already earmarked for the GE promotion. In a nutshell, Western interventions deplete the country's already limited resource.

GE Backlash. Investigating GE activities is imperative because of the unrelenting onslaught of contentious concepts, misinformation, and indoctrination, particularly affecting unsuspecting Filipino citizens. Radical notions such as "state-raised children," "child rights and freedom," and abortion disturb traditional parenting and early childhood (Riddell, 2016; Cruz, 2021; Evon, 2016; Lindsey & Sarri, 1992; Bolt, 2012; Feeney, Christensen, & Moravcik, 2006; Sala, 1978; DSWD- Bureau of Child and Youth Welfare, 1995). Unfortunately, in contrast to developed nations, Oriental countries like the Philippines lack an effective defense mechanism against these (cf. Dimmock v. Secretary of State for Education and Skills, 2007; Bolt, 2012; Wilson, 2010; Sheppard, 2009; The Lord Monckton Foundation, 2012). More disturbing is the propagation of GE as a distorted version of individual freedom, by equating women's rights solely with human rights (Ludwig, 2018; MacArthur, 1981a; McKinstry, 2016). Ironically, in fact, human rights campaigns solely center on women - an intrinsic practice of inequality. Furthermore, the West persistently espouses extreme feminist ideas including racism, coupling to GW concerns, street violence politics, and the perplexing "gender policy" by the US democratic faction, which alienates segments even of American women (Hoffman, LeBlanc, & Sullivan, 2021).

Lastly, GE proponents seem to overlook that categorizing women as a disadvantaged or vulnerable sector is fallacious and effectively competes with genuinely marginalized groups for special attention and funding (cf. Conley, 2020). Furthermore, the GE propaganda showcases inconsistency by promoting the cultural distinctiveness of gender relations (one society's gender norms cannot be imposed on another) yet, egalitarianism is being enforced on other nations. The purported equality espoused by GE is paradoxical.

Addressing the Gap. Given these dynamics, backlashes against the GE movement are anticipated (e.g., Robinson, 2018). Hence, rather than aligning with gender enthusiasts, this study finds greater value in exploring the unvoiced and unexplored facet of the movement - the taxpayers' feedback. It has become imperative to validate whether ordinary citizens genuinely share the perspective of global elites, who view GE as some pressing national issue requiring immediate attention. In the main, grounding the entire GE ideology in public opinion assumes critical significance because the existing literature not only exposes the pervasive flaws but also overlooks the genuine consequences of contentious concepts.

Research Objective and Paradigm

A conceptual framework guides this research's trajectory and plays an integral role in addressing the research objectives of understanding GE within the broader ASEAN context. Prodded by the absence of relevant studies, this study banks on direct participants engagement as a means of capturing the cultural tapestry, local and shared dynamics, and adaptive processes prevalent in the ASEAN region. This ultimately paves the way for an in-depth exploration of the Oriental perspective on GE.

The crux of the present investigation revolves around a pivotal question: Why must GE command the paramount concern of Filipinos? The endeavor to provide answers necessitates a systematic examination of taxpayers' perceptions, beginning with a specific group of Ilonggo respondents. Figure 1 presents the identified research variables, with the constructs LOU, DOA, DOC, and PBE forming the dimensions of the dependent variable, which are aligned to the respondents' perceptions as in the study objectives (refer to Chapter I, Section 3). These constructs are influenced by the respondents' diverse backgrounds representing 21 independent variables. As shown in the figure, the respondent's background serves as the 21 main determinants (independent variables) of the multivariate dependent variable, the respondents' perceptions about gender equality (GE), which are finally categorized into 4 levels or constructs: The respondents' *Level of Understanding* (LOU), *Degree of Acceptance* (DOA), *Degree of Concern* (DOC) or urgency, and *Perceived Benefits* (PBE) or value appreciation. Acronyms: STAT- marital status, BIRTH- place of birth, STAY- years of residence in Iloilo, ADD- address, RELGN- religion, PRAY- church visits per year, COLL- tertiary school, GRADS- graduate school, DGREE- education level, GESBJ- number of GE subjects taken, GESEM- number of GE seminars attended, TRAING- non-academic trainings, JOBNAT- nature of present job, HEADF- head(s) of family, EARNF- family bread earner(s), CHILM- number of male children, CHILDF- number of female children, GAYX- number of LGBTI children, relatives, and friends exposed to. Variable labels are more fully described in Table 7, Chapter IV.

The Perception Model

The mathematical expression that governs the relationship between the variables of the paradigm (Figure 1) assumes a dependent variable that is a function of independent variables in a linear fashion (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Research Paradigm. (See text for acronyms.)

Figure 2. Linear Perception Model.

$$P = \sum (c_n \cdot B_n) + R$$

Where;

P - dependent variable (a multivariate)

B - independent variable

c - constant or loading

n - level or dimension ($n=1$ to 4)

R - residual

The model relates *perception P* to 21 *background variables B*, only four particular combinations of which actually define the four constructs (levels or dimensions) of the multivariate dependent variable, i.e., $\sum (c_n \cdot B_n)$, $n=1$ to 4. The rest of the combinations are accounted for by *residuals R* which, in the assumed linear model, are treated as meaningless, irrelevant constructs. The four constructs of perception correspond to the study objectives spelled out in Section 3 of Chapter 1. Extracting these constructs was the computational objective of this study.

Study Hypotheses

In order to quantitatively differentiate the influence of the background information (21 independent variables) on perception, these propositions were tested:

1. There are no significant differences in GE perceptions when differentiated according to the background variables.
2. None of the background variables can significantly explain or predict the GE perceptions.

Table 1 helps tie up the study objectives to the identified research variables in Figure 1 and, further, to the measures and methods of analysis used in this study.

Research Design

The investigation was exploratory in nature, and the appropriate research design chosen employed mixed quantitative-qualitative methodologies. To ensure successful conduct of the research, the geographical locale was strategically situated within Iloilo Province, identified for its availability of essential manpower resources and research facilities. The primary means of data collection was the survey, complemented by in-depth interviews of gender experts, and a documentary analysis

of online resources. The survey was facilitated using a tailored questionnaire, while the interviews adhered to a structured checklist.

Table 1

Table of specifications connecting the study objectives to the methods of analysis, via the measured constructs and the natures of measurement

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVE OR QUESTION ASKED	VARIABLE OR CONSTRUCT MEASURED	NATURE OF MEASUREMENT	ANALYSIS
What is the LOU?	LOU	Percentage Scale	descriptive statistics - AVE, MODE
		Open-Ended Response	textual analysis, coding, binning - MODE
What is the DOA?	DOA	Percentage Scale	descriptive statistics - AVE, MODE
		Open-Ended Response	textual analysis, coding, binning - MODE
What is the DOC?	DOC	Percentage Scale	descriptive statistics - AVE, MODE
		Open-Ended Response	textual analysis, coding, binning - MODE
What is the PBE?	PBE	Percentage Scale	descriptive statistics - AVE, MODE
		Open-Ended Response	textual analysis, coding, binning - MODE
Study Hypotheses: Influence of the respondents' background on their survey responses.	Background Variables (9 of 12)	Open-Ended Response	coding, descriptive statistics - AVE
	Background Multi-level Variables (12 of 21)		coding, binning, and Hypothesis Testing: 1) One-Way ANOVA 2) Multi-Regression

The Study Participants

An inclusion-exclusion criteria restricted the survey respondents to individuals who qualified as Ilonggo residents - the target population. Residence within the province for a minimum of three years, irrespective of continuity, was perceived as significant immersion into Ilonggo culture and norms. Recognizing the sensitive nature of the GE concept, minors — defined as those below 18 years of age — were deliberately excluded from the study. The participant demographic naturally coalesced around university students, educators, and staff, effectively representing the study's accessible population. The interviewees, identified as GE experts, possessed a minimum of a bachelor's degree in the social sciences, coupled with teaching experience in GE or related disciplines. Substantial involvement in GE-focused orientation programs, workshops, or seminars was additionally admitted as qualifying expertise.

Selection Criteria

A maximum of 60 survey respondents was decided upon as final sample size after a rigorous consideration of several crucial factors. Given the logistical constraints and the prevailing pandemic, expanding the number of survey participants beyond this limit would be impractical and thus potentially detrimental to the study. Viewed in the context of the province's substantial population of 1,126,679 (NSO, 2010), a larger number of participants would also compromise the depth and comprehension of the study. The decision, while seemingly modest, was not taken lightly but, instead, made to reflect a meticulous balance between strategic representation and constraints of resources and circumstances.

The selection of respondents was aimed at sufficiently capturing a rich perspective on GE acknowledging the diversity within the oriental ASEAN context (i.e., the intricate web of cultural, societal, and historical nuances that influence perspectives on GE). The aim was not about exhaustiveness but about delving deeper into the intricate layers of the perception and understanding. In this context, the selection of qualified respondents aligned well with the qualitative nature of the study objectives, which sought to explore depth rather than breadth. A conscientious trade-off had to prioritize in-depth insights over sheer numbers of participants, which favored the richer exploration of the topic given the constraints of the study.

Accordingly, a *stratified-convenience* sampling strategy was employed (cf. Cochran, 1963) as it complemented well the inclusion-exclusion criteria. This approach allowed the specification of roughly the same numbers of male and female representatives from progressive towns (1st or 2nd Class) versus repressed towns (4th or 5th Class), a condition met by three target sites – Northern Iloilo State University (NISU) in the northern town of Estancia, John B. Lacson Foundation Maritime University (JBLFMU) in Iloilo City, and the University of the Philippines in the Visayas (UPV) in the southern town of Miagao, Iloilo. Stratification with respect to other factors such as address, occupation, income, etc. only improved data characteristics. In theory, while non-probabilistic, convenience sampling is a practical recourse and uncomplicated, but can yield meaningful results when one is mindful of biases.

The Survey Instrument

To capture the multidimensional facets of the respondents' perceptions of GE, a researcher-designed survey questionnaire was developed, particularly addressing the four study questions (Chapter I, Section 3). The instrument blended quantitative

metrics with open-ended textual (qualitative) inquiries, effectively simulating the interview process. The final instrument materialized as a single Microsoft Excel file, divided into two parts (Appendix A). Specific instructions were provided for each part including a statement about the survey's purpose. To encourage accurate responses, respondents were allowed sufficient time to complete the questionnaire thoughtfully, devoid of hesitations. They were given the freedom to submit their returns via email or Facebook messenger.

Part 1 of the questionnaire had 46 items, meant to capture the confidential background of the respondents. This portion was supplied with illustrative fictional text for clarity. The main substance of the instrument was in Part 2, subdivided into sections A to D. Each section comprised 12 pairs of items — quantitative (scale or metric) and open-ended textual (categorical) — resulting to a comprehensive total of 96 items. Section B uniquely featured an additional item (refer to Appendix A). The four sections were carefully designed to unearth the four embedded constructs: Level of Understanding (LOU), Degree of Acceptance (DOA), Degree of Concern (DOC), and Perceived Benefits (PBE), in direct correspondence with the four study questions (Chapter I, Section 3).

All items in the questionnaire were digitally locked, except for the placeholders, which required the respondent's inputs. Some hard copies were additionally produced for certain respondents who found it more convenient to manually accomplish the questionnaire.

Research Procedures

In the main, data collection utilized a survey questionnaire, personal interview, and online document search. Both the survey and interview were predominantly conducted in a telecommuting mode.

The survey, serving as the primary data source, employed a researcher-designed questionnaire, which underwent an initial validation review by a panel of instrument experts (referred to as jurors) from the Western Visayas State University in Iloilo City. This university is acknowledged as a Center of Excellence for Education in Region 6. Upon approval of its *juror validity*, the instrument was distributed to prospective respondents.

To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a pretest was conducted as soon as 30 completed survey returns were received. The reliability value found, $R=0.831$, indicated a high level of reliability. Consequently, questionnaire administration proceeded until a total of 60 survey questionnaires were recovered. Although the majority of tasks were carried out remotely, and the progress was moderately slow, further degree of success was achieved. Subsequently, instrument reliability was recalculated, and the somewhat subjective juror validity was re-evaluated through confirmatory factor and discriminant-classification analyses (detailed below).

Since the crux of the data processing involved the 60 survey returns, a flowchart is shown to visually outlines the sequential steps (Figure 3). These steps commenced upon the completion of Parts 1 (Background) and 2 (Survey Proper) of the questionnaires. Early results included the reevaluated and confirmed reliability (R) and validity (V). The revised reliability, based on 60 completed responses, affirmed the instrument's high reliability. Notably, the Guttman option of the SPSS software yielded six reliable measures, each accompanied by corresponding lower bounds for true

reliability. The third estimate, $R=0.827$, closely mirrored the previously computed value (see Appendix C.1). Regarding validity, a confirmatory analysis superseded the initial juror validity through another advanced statistical technique. Factor/principal component analysis identified 4 to 5 components accounting for approximately 70% of the data variance (see Appendix C.2). The scree plot of factors showcased the influence of these components on the cumulative variance. A varimax rotation did not enhance the results and warrants no further discussion. Detailed loadings from factor analysis identified the survey items significantly influencing variance. Most important, the combined statistical analyses provided instrument validation beyond the initial juror assessment.

Another outcome of the procedures was the resolution of the study hypotheses, which was originally posed to understand the impact of the independent variables (referred to as background) on the survey responses (the dependent variable represented by AVE60). Hypothesis 1 was addressed using One-way ANOVA, while Hypothesis 2 through Multiple Regression Analysis. Descriptive statistics for both questionnaire parts were supplementary outcomes. The primary output comprised of condensed survey findings, presented in four tables that concisely summarized the responses to the research questions.

A rationale for acknowledging instrument validity pertains to the determination of the four constructs – LOU, DOA, DOC, and PBE – as they aligned with and embodied the study objectives. Figure 4 illustrates the distinctiveness of these constructs relative to each other. While individual items were dispersed around the respective group means, four well-defined groupings emerged. The discriminant table (Appendix C.3) demonstrated perfect classification of items under each intended construct, confirmed the robust construct validity of the survey instrument.

Figure 3. Flowchart of the survey data processing procedures. Ellipses denote outcomes of the steps. AVE60 represents the average of 48 numeric items across 60 respondents, serving as the dependent variable in the ANOVA and Multi-regression analyses of the 12 independent background variables (Figure 1). RA– Reliability Analysis. FA– Factor Analysis. DA– Discriminant/Classification Analysis. R– Reliability. V– Validity. H1- Hypothesis 1. H2– Hypothesis 2.

A mixed quantitative-qualitative approach was likewise consistently adopted in handling the data. Numeric responses were processed straightforwardly, whereas non-numeric (textual) responses were specially treated. Considerable efforts were expended to digitally code these latter responses for subsequent analyses. Subsequently, iterative paraphrasing condensed the raw responses into meaningful keywords, facilitating their grouping and storage. The iterative process was sustained until the most representative set of keywords was achieved. Overall, the subsequent statistical analyses included descriptive and frequency statistics, reliability, factor and discriminant-classification analyses, and inferential tests employing One-Way ANOVA

and linear multiple regression. These analyses became feasible only after converting the non-numeric responses into numerical modes.

Supplementary interview data played a significant role in clarifying ambiguous survey responses. These data also helped identify and exclude unrelated responses, thus improving data quality. Moreover, the interview data guided the historical analysis employed during the literature review process.

Figure 4. The clustering of 48 items about the four constructs (LOU, DOA, DOC, and PBE) as revealed by Discriminant Analysis. These constructs correspond to the four sections of the survey questionnaire, aligned to the study objectives. Output derived using the SPSS software (SPSS, 1998).

Chapter IV

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

This chapter of seven sections discusses at length the results of the survey, their interpretation, and analysis, tightly within the context of the four study objectives. Thus, four sections are devoted to resolving these objectives (1) Level of Understanding of GE, (2) Degree of Acceptance of GE, (3) Degree of Concern about GE, and (4) Perceived Benefits of GE. Additional sections further discuss the following: (5) Respondents' Background, (6) The Influential Factors, (7) Explaining the Factors, and (8) A Synoptic Analysis, which wraps up the contribution and implications of this study.

Section 1 discusses the responses to the first 12 items (Section A) of the questionnaire and pertains to the respondents' *Level of Understanding* of the GE concept.

Section 2 discusses the responses to the next 12 items (Section B) of the questionnaire regarding the *Degree of Acceptance* of the respondents of the GE concept.

Section 3 discusses the responses to the third set of 12 items (Section C) of the questionnaire and addresses the *Degree of Concern* of the respondents about the GE concept.

Section 4 discusses the responses to the last 12 items (Section D) of the questionnaire and pertains to the *Perceived Benefits* of the GE concept.

Section 5 elaborates on the background profile of the respondents revealing their demographic characteristics and attributes.

Section 6 examines the influence of the independent (background) variables on the dependent variable (survey responses) in order to explain the study hypotheses and, in particular, identify those background variables that were the strongest influence to the participants' responses.

Section 7 provides a summary of the salient findings derived from the survey analyses. An overview of insights extracted from experts' interviews is also presented.

Reactions to the survey are systematically organized in Tables 3 to 6 as a concise means of answering the four study questions. Each table shows the average and modal responses to the individual queries, along with the corresponding modal explanations. The average was utilized as the primary measure of central tendency of the responses, supplemented by the mode to reflect the response frequency. The explanations seen in the second column of the tables are arranged according to these frequencies. These were keywords progressively condensed from the respondents' raw narratives, subsequently categorized by meaning or context, and ranked by frequency. All values are expressed in percentages (%) and interpreted following the rubric shown in Table 2.

To maintain coherence relative to the study objectives, the discussions of the main results were summed up in the four tables of findings, Tables 3 to 6, i.e., likewise divided into four sections. The following discussions of these tables abstain from redundant repetitions. Rather, the focus is presently on rephrasing the detailed tabular information by way of extracting findings relevant to the study objectives. Each pair of values in parentheses indicates the average and mode of response (both in %), while a single enclosed value indicates the mode or frequency (also in %) of the associated explanation(s) shown in the last columns of each table. Relevant annotations with citations precede the presentation of results hinting at their implications.

Table 2

Rubric for interpreting the numeric responses to the survey. The scale ranges from 0% (indicating negative response or complete disagreement) to 100% (indicating positive response or complete agreement). This scale is popular and thus convenient to interpret

SCALE INTERVAL (%)	DEGREE OF AGREEMENT
0	none; lowest
0.5-24.5	very low
25	low
25.5-49.5	quite low
50	neutral; undecided
50.5-74.5	quite high
75	high
75.5-99.5	very high
100	total; highest

Level of Understanding of GE

By way of answering the first study question, Table 3 provides insights into the respondents' perspectives of the GE concept and related issues. This section presents the findings related to the level of understanding of GE of Filipino respondents covering their perception of the definition of GE, sources of knowledge, awareness of gender issues, understanding of the distinction between gender and sex, views on LGBTI representation, perceptions of the impact of the GE movement, and their notion of "equality" within GE. Additionally, it delves into their awareness of the budget allocation and the constitutional perspective on GE.

Definition of GE. Knowing how respondents perceive the definition of GE is crucial in gauging their understanding of the concept. Cultural and societal norms can significantly influence this perception (Hofstede, 1983), and the respondents' interpretations of GE are further shaped by their exposure to local discussions, international influences, or religious beliefs (Kabeer, 2005). The present results show

Table 3

Level of Understanding of GE perceived by respondents, summarized by their averaged responses and the ranked modes of their corresponding explanations. The 12 queries formed the first section of the survey questionnaire

QUERY	AVE	MDE	MODES OF EXPLANATIONS
A1 Do you know what is gender equality?	70.3	100	73.4 equal treatment and opportunities 23.3 only claims or assertions of equality 3.3 others
A2 In terms of percentage, how much do you actually know about gender equality?	65.0	80	46.8 media and online 25.0 seminars and trainings 15.0 friends and other people 10.0 school and books 3.2 others
A3 Are you also aware that gender equality is all about promoting women's welfare?	84.3	100	38.6 according to advocates and seminars 33.5 because of more laws favoring women 21.4 to recognize women's role and contribution 6.5 because of violence against women
A4 Is gender different from sex?	33.3	0	50.6 no difference/the same 46.0 sex is biological; gender is social or cultural 3.4 others
A5 Are lesbians, gays, bisexuals, transgenders, and intersexuals (LGBTIs) other kinds of gender or sex?	23.3	0	70.0 no, anyone can only be either man or woman 26.7 yes, other sexuality, choice, or orientation 3.3 others
A6 Are you aware of some gender issues or problems?	61.2	100	53.4 discrim. & abuses of women & LGBTIs 23.3 equal suscept. of all- should be no issues 18.3 LGBTIs getting pushy and restless 5.0 others
A7 Do you know that 5% of the budget of government agencies is mandated for the promotion of gender equality?	52.0	100	55.2 school, institution, or office 26.6 research, circulars, seminars, meetings, or trainings 18.2 no idea; unsure
A8 Do you know how the funds for the gender equality program are being spent?	45.1	0	43.5 women empowerment, research, and extension projects 33.4 GAD promotion seminars and trainings for women only 23.1 no idea
A9 Do you know what 'equality' is all about in gender equality?	63.7	90	43.6 equal rights and opportunities for men and women 28.0 equal rights and opportunities for all [genders] 26.6 no inequality of genders to begin with 1.8 equal opportunities and rights for women
A10 Is gender equality the cause or origin of equal rights of and opportunities for men and women in our society?	21.4	0	46.9 no, inequality existed before GAD; not an issue 31.5 don't think so; never the case 11.6 all must have equal rights and just treatment 10.0 no idea
A11 Is gender equality also the cause or origin of equal rights of and opportunities for LGBTIs in our society?	22.8	0	40.0 misguided information; just a claim 33.2 no man-woman inequality; LGBTI unacceptable to religion 26.8 all rights offered in life and in the Constitution
A12 Does the Constitution speak of equality for all, whether men or women, incl. the LGBTIs?	79.3	100	90.0 all has equal rights & protection of law 10.0 only men and women - not LGBTIs

Table 4

Degree of Acceptance of GE perceived by respondents, summarized by their averaged responses and the ranked modes of their corresponding explanations. The 12 queries formed the second section of the survey questionnaire

QUERY	AVE	MDE	MODES OF EXPLANATIONS
B1 Are there roles, tasks, or functions in the society that are better performed by men than women, or vice versa? <i>*the case for women:</i>	84.3	100	66.8 jobs requiring strength- mechanical, hard labor, construction, so on. 30.0 jobs exposed to dangers - farming, fishing, military, security 3.2 anybody can perform anything *45.1 housewife, housekeeper *36.7 mother, childcare *18.2 pre-school, caregiver, office work, hospitality
B2 Do you still accept that fathers - not mothers - must be treated as heads of their respective families?	83.2	100	38.6 it's the Christian belief, tradition 33.4 father must be the sole head/foundation 28.0 except for single moms or egalitarian societies
B3 Does our society actually favor men over women?	18.3	0	61.8 it's not the case; no reason to; no discrimination 18.0 only in cases to protect women e.g., physical labor 16.9 the opposite because of GE; Muslim soc. 3.3 men actually cherish women
B4 Do you agree that women are being oppressed, abused, or marginalized in our society?	21.0	0	46.7 false campaign; all equal or can be abused 26.7 few isolated reports; maybe sometimes 26.6 some women even dominate; men also abused but just silent
B5 Must women be treated as a separate special sector of our society like orphans, indigents, senior citizens, or PWDs?	4.8	0	70.4 no good/special reason to; being a woman is not a disability 18.4 GE means equality & no special treatment 11.2 only of single moms or other special cases
B6 Must our society specially promote awareness of violence against women only?	13.7	0	50.0 GE is equal. for all; women not that special 40.0 men/anyone can be violated or abused 10.0 to stop violence; gov't must focus on VAW
B7 Is it alright to have more gender or sex categories other than the trad. male & female?	14.4	0	46.9 only 2 biol. sexes; as per tradition & Bible 33.1 nonsense; unnec.; confusion; troublesome 20.0 out of respect; sex not a personal choice
B8 Do you accept that the gender or sex of an individual be based only on biological makeup?	90.0	100	55.2 "What else?"; natural, universal; God-prescribed 41.8 science basis; sex det. at birth- not feelings 3.0 humans may undergo fluidity
B9 Must an individual be officially & totally free to choose and declare his/her pref. gender?	41.4	0	66.9 sex and the sex organs already set from conception to birth 33.1 env'l., personal will, choice, or right but must only be responsible
B10 Must parents agree that their child's sex or gender be decided only by them when they grow old enough?	39.7	0	88.9 must guide children to God's truth about their true sexes; sex is obvious at birth 11.1 there is freedom of who we are
B11 To protect their health, can women choose, for example, not to breastfeed, or even abort a baby?	35.6	0	65.3 immoral; a sin; inhuman; very irresponsible 31.5 only if mother's life is endangered; other special health purposes 3.2 yes, to protect women's health
B12 Do you agree that there must be a gender equality movement in our country?	25.2	0	71.7 money pit; nonsense; unnecessary; Constitution already exists for everybody 18.3 reminder only to respect women/other genders 10.0 no – we must honor the traditional concept of sex in the family and society

Table 5

Degree of Concern about GE perceived by respondents, summarized by their averaged responses and the ranked modes of their corresponding explanations. The 12 queries formed the third section of the survey questionnaire

	QUERY	AVE	MDE	MODES OF EXPLANATIONS	
C1	Is gender equality a crucial matter that you must spend time and resources on?	19.5	0	50.1 36.9 13.0	sensational but trivial; Constitution covers it there are far more imp. matters to attend to to have sense of empathy; empower women; fight climate change
C2	Do you worry whenever there are more male than female politicians, businessmen, teachers, heroes, musicians, etc.?	2.8	0	53.3 46.7	can't see any problem; not worrisome; nonsense opportunities are open for everyone; each has unique skills; far-fetched
C3	Are you worried that gender equality actually disapproves of the patriarchal (traditional) Christian religion?	80.7	100	70.2 18.1 11.7	bizarre; shocking; against tradition & religion women empowered; society is changing no idea
C4	Is it really important for women to prove that they can do whatever men can do, or vice versa?	16.2	0	80.0 20.0	pointless; man or woman is unique; nonsense no- as long as capable; acceptance nec.
C5	Are you getting concerned about the growing numbers of LGBTIs?	69.4	100	58.6 25.0 16.4	yes - troublesome; overacting; pointless genders hormonal, and spiritual crisis no- as long as they respect others; can do what they like to their bodies yes- unbiblical; disrupting the natural order
C6	Will you be worried if women are given the rights not to breastfeed or even abort a baby?	86.4	100	78.5 21.5	yes- crime against life; morally wrong; against Christianity yes- but depends on the reason; breastfeeding but not killing
C7	Are you generally interested in knowing more about gender equality?	40.5	0	61.9 38.1	irrational; waste of money; nonsense; irrelevant; enough; disinterested to learn critically; to understand more any benefits from the use of money
C8	Are you worried that gender equality is being elevated as a national priority problem?	90.6	100	70.3 18.5 8.2 3.0	waste of taxes on a nonproblem; there are far more important problems GE is not a true equality movement; emphasizes women's welfare only GE funds can be used instead for other probs. will increase national resources; neutral view
C9	Is the economy truly dependent on whether or not men and women are equally represented in the society?	7.0	0	75.0 25.0	economy since long ago never dependent on sex economy depends instead on factors like corruption, jobs, leaders
C10	Do you care if gender equality is taught in schools to your young children?	84.0	100	51.8 25.0 23.2	inappropriate; will corrupt children early awareness, respect, and equality doubtful if it's about respect; mislead kids from Christian values
C11	Are you worried with the fact that a part of your taxes goes to the promotion of gender equality?	81.4	100	90.0 10.0	unwise spending; a waste of funds to a nonexistent problem; nonsense helps promote equality; if money is well spent
C12	Is gender equality as worrisome as the country's problems on corruption, poverty, and criminality?	6.4	0	80.0 11.7 8.3	GE far from being a problem at all; a fanfare; nonsense; Constitution already protects all GE a problem only if focused on women alone; promotes equality contradicts the Bible; not same as other probs

Table 6

Perceived Benefits of GE perceived by respondents, summarized by their averaged responses and the ranked modes of their corresponding explanations. The 12 queries formed the last section of the survey questionnaire

QUERY	AVE	MDE	MODES OF EXPLANATIONS
D1 Have there been benefits (if any) derived from promoting gender equality in our country?	22.9	0	80.2 none; imaginary; no idea of any 18.4 opportunities for women; equal job opport. 1.4 decrease abuse of women; happy comm.
D2 On the other hand, have been there any bad effects (if any) derived from promoting gender equality?	76.6	100	65.2 caused factions; conflicts; corruption of values; wasted or misdirected resources 21.7 men are prejudiced or abused in favor of women; violence 13.1 GE movement is positive; none that I know
D3 Do you know who are truly benefiting from the promotion of gender equality (if any)?	62.1	100	76.9 advocates; promoters; women; LGBTIs; NGOs; research institutions; perverts 11.9 all of us; oppressed children 11.2 no idea
D4 Do you think that gender equality is really improving our economy?	22.3	0	81.8 no contribution; economy the same; no connection; irrelevant 15.1 more jobs/positions for women; free marriage 3.1 not sure
D5 Do you think that gender equality is also benefiting politics?	77.7	100	65.4 issues politicized; funds for campaigns or elections 23.2 no idea; irrelevant to politics 10.0 diversity in leadership; democracy 1.4 GE brings peace
D6 Do you think that gender equality is truly benefiting our educational system?	24.9	0	50.1 only more women, LGBTI, & GE advocates; it's corrupting learners 25.1 no effect; no role; no contribution 13.3 education now more equal and open 11.5 maybe; no idea
D7 Do you think that gender equality is contributing to science?	20.9	0	83.6 propaganda- not science; unnecessary it's social sci.; there are women scientists 8.4 not really sure 8.0
D8 Do you think that gender equality is benefiting your traditional beliefs or religion?	10.4	0	81.9 no benefits at all; against religion & tradn. 11.8 no idea 6.3 women helping churches; some changes
D9 Has our society actually improved because of the gender equality movement?	21.6	0	73.7 just worsened society; society has improved without it; a fake problem 16.1 equal opportunities; peace; safer society; more respect of rights 10.2 no idea
D10 Have you personally benefited from the gender equality movement?	18.3	0	73.3 no benefits; nuisance; pestered me; seminars are waste of time; useless 15.1 don't participate in the movement; just attended some seminars 11.6 I am an LGBTI member; more roles for women; GAD programs in schools
D11 Will children benefit from learning gender equality?	28.2	0	66.7 pointless; children have no appreciation; creates confusion; harmful 16.7 to know equality and tolerance 16.6 no idea
D12 Must the government continue spending its 5% budget for gender equality because it is worth our money?	16.5	0	88.8 no way; redirect to other priorities; waste of funds; corruption; not worthy of funds for the good of the society; equal rights for all; for peace 11.2

that a significant majority (70.3, 100) of the study participants quite strongly agreed that GE is defined as "equal treatment and opportunities" (73.4) and as asserted "claims of equality" (23.3). A minority (3.3) offered alternative definitions.

Sources of GE Information. The sources of knowledge about GE shed light about the accessibility and dissemination of information regarding the advocacy. Understanding whether or not participants primarily rely on these sources provides insights into the influence of GE awareness campaigns (UN Women, 2015). The present survey showed that the respondents quite strongly claimed (65, 80) to acquire knowledge about GE from various sources - online and media (46.8), seminars and training (25.0), friends and acquaintances (15.0), books and educational institutions (10.0), or some unspecified means (3.2). Further, in perceiving GE, the respondents were very aware (84.3, 100) that GE is confined to promoting women's welfare. They associated this with advocacy efforts through seminars (38.6), additional laws favoring women (33.5), campaigns for women's recognition (21.4), and VAW (6.5).

Gender versus Sex. The respondents' distinction of gender as opposed to sex is essential, as any position or misconception can spawn biases and stereotypes (Butler, 2006). Their grasp of the concepts of gender in relation to sex may suggest to gender advocates certain areas where their campaign efforts may focus (Connell, 2014). In this study, a substantial number of respondents quite strongly disagreed (33.0, 0) that gender differs from sex (50.6). Further, others viewed sex as biological and gender as a social or cultural construct (46.0). A few offered incongruous responses (3.4).

LGBTI Representation. Gender advocates may also consider the respondents' viewpoints on LGBTI representation to reflect societal acceptance and attitudes toward the concept of gender diversity (UNDP, USAID, 2014). Cultural norms, religious beliefs, and exposure to inclusive narratives in media and education may play a significant role in shaping these views (Herek, 2014). Current study respondents strongly disagreed (23.3,0) that LGBTIs must represent another sex or gender. The majority (70.0) insisted that individuals can only be categorized as male or female, while a minority (26.7) still believed LGBTI individuals represent another sexuality, choice, or orientation. A few respondents made no comment (3.3). Moreover, regarding their general perception of GE issues, the majority (61.2, 100) of respondents claimed to be quite aware of popularized gender issues or problems. Approximately half (53.4) of them associated these issues with a popularized phrase, "discrimination and abuses of women and LGBTIs." Some even believed that such issues did not exist, as everyone had "equal susceptibility" (23.3), while others characterized LGBTIs as mere "pushy and restless" (18.3). The rest of the respondents offered irrelevant responses (5.0).

Perception of "Equality" in GE. Just how the respondents interpret "equality" within the context of GE is crucial as this may reveal whether they attribute it to their common interpretation of equality as associated with equal opportunities, rights, or outcomes, or whether they perceive any conflicts or trade-offs among these concepts (Sen, 1987). The present study reveals that respondents quite understood (63.7, 90) the concept of "equality" within GE as matters about equal rights and opportunities for men and women (43.6) or, equivalently, for all genders (28.0). Some even argued that there was no inequality to address in the first place (26.6), along with a small fraction

asserting that equality meant equal opportunities and rights, but intended only for women (1.8).

Impact of the GE Movement. The respondents' understanding of the impact of the GE movement allows for an evaluation of the movement's effectiveness or its degree of public reception (Budig, 2014). Positive perceptions may indicate that awareness campaigns have been successful, while negative perceptions may signal problems or plain disagreement (Duflo, 2012). Present respondents strongly disagreed (21.4, 0) that the GE movement was responsible for achieving equality between men and women in society. Many believed that gender inequality predated the movement (46.9) or that it was never an issue, as everyone already had equal rights and fair treatment (31.5). Some respondents had no specific opinion (10.0). In like manner, the group strongly disagreed (22.8, 0) that the movement contributed to the equality of rights and opportunities for LGBTIs. Some attributed this view to misinformation (40.0), religious beliefs that reject LGBTI acceptance (33.2), or the belief that equal rights were already guaranteed by the Constitution (26.8%).

Funding and Constitutional Perspectives. The respondents' awareness of the GE budget allocation vis-a-vis their constitutional perspective on GE provides insights into the rationale of integrating gender-related policies and priorities at governmental levels. Moreover, it may also reflect the extent to which constitutional principles are reflected in practice (Weldon, 2006). Present survey respondents expressed confidence (52.0, 100) in the existence of a 5% budget allocation for the GE promotion. They cited knowing about this from schools, institutions, or offices (55.2), circulars, seminars, meetings, research, or training (26.6), and unspecified sources (18.2). However, they were uncertain (45.1, 0) about how these funds were being spent.

Some believed the funds were allocated only for women's empowerment, research, and extension projects (43.5) or GAD promotion seminars and training for women (33.4), while others had no specific insights (23.1). Moreover, with regard to constitutional perspective, the respondents strongly affirmed (79.3,100) that the Constitution already recognizes equality for all, encompassing men, women, and LGBTIs. They believed that everyone had equal rights and protection under the law (90.0), although a minority still suggested that LGBTIs were not explicitly mentioned in the legal provisions (10.0).

Degree of Acceptance of GE

Table 4 presents the respondents' perspectives on the second study question that primarily addressed the acceptance of ideas propagated by the predominantly feminist GE movement. Particularly, it explores the degree of acceptance among Filipino respondents of the various gender-related aspects, ideas about the traditional gender roles, family leadership, perceptions of oppression and marginalization, awareness of violence against women, recognition of traditional gender categories, the biological basis of gender or sex, freedom of gender choice, parental guidance on gender, breastfeeding, abortion, and the existence of the GE movement. The expressed viewpoints reflected a diversity of unpopular perspectives on these issues.

Gender Roles and Family Leadership. Assessing the respondents' views on traditional gender roles and family leadership can uncover the prevailing attitudes towards gender norms within familial and societal contexts (Eagly, 2000). These attitudes may be strongly influenced by cultural and religious factors (Davies & Thate, 2017). In this regard, the respondents strongly agreed (84.3, 100) that certain tasks are more suitable for either men or women. Most believed that jobs requiring strength

or heavy physical exertion (66.8) or those involving potential dangers (30.0) are better suited for men. Jobs considered more appropriate for women included such traditional roles as wife and housekeeping (41.5), motherhood and childcare (36.7), and relatively lighter tasks like caregiving and office work (18.3). A small minority believed that individuals of either gender could perform any task (3.2). On family leadership, respondents strongly agreed (83.2, 100) that the father must head the family due to Christian beliefs and tradition (38.6) and because he is seen as the family's foundation (33.4). Exceptions were noted in cases of single mothers and egalitarian societies (28.0). However, to clarify, respondents strongly disagreed (18.3, 0) with the usual assertion that men are being favored over women in the society. A majority (61.8) asserted that such favoritism does not exist and that any indication of it is a result of the need to protect women, especially from physically demanding work (18.0). Some even believed that, due to GE promotion, women are now even treated more favorably, citing similarities with Muslim societies (16.9). A few respondents further expressed the belief that Oriental men genuinely cherish women (3.3%).

Oppression and Marginalization. The respondents' perceptions of oppression and marginalization in relation to gender may reveal their notion of gender-based inequalities and discrimination (Connell, 2014). Understanding whether they recognize these issues can inform advocates of the right efforts to address them (Hartmann, 1979). Regarding these issues, the respondents strongly rejected (21.0, 0) the usual claim that women are oppressed, abused, or marginalized in society. They attributed this perception to false campaigns or instances where the concept of equality is misused (46.7). Some acknowledged isolated reports (26.7) but also mentioned scenarios wherein women dominate while men remain silent (26.6). Consequently, respondents strongly disagreed (4.8, 0) with the proposition that women must be

treated as a special disadvantaged group the likes of orphans, indigents, senior citizens, or persons with disabilities (PWDs). They emphasized that being a woman is not a disability (70.4). In their view, GE represents "equality," which truly implies no special treatment (18.4). However, they also recognized valid cases, such as those of single mothers (11.2).

Violence Against Women (VAW). Investigating the respondents' awareness of violence against women is essential to the fundamental contextualization of GE (Garcia-Moreno, 2006). It may indicate whether or not the educational and awareness campaigns on the issue have been effective in raising consciousness about certain gender-related problems thought of as critical by the movement (Heise, 1994). However, there was strong disagreement (13.7, 0) against the promotion of awareness about violence solely against women. Respondents asserted that GE should mean equality for all (50.0) and that anyone, including men, can be a victim of violence and abuse (40.0). Nonetheless, a minority believed that to combat violence, the government should focus exclusively on VAW (10.0).

Gender Categories. How respondents recognize traditional gender categories can provide insights into the preservation or evolution of cultural norms related to gender (Connell, 2014). This study clarified that the respondents strongly disagreed (14.4, 0) with the idea of introducing sex categories other than the traditional male and female category. The majority (46.9) maintained that there are only two biological sexes, as per the science, tradition, and religious texts. Many considered the other categorizations as nonsensical, unnecessary, and potentially confusing (33.1). Some argued that sex is not a matter of personal choice and that any alternative categorization is mentioned only out of respect (20.0). Regarding the basis of gender or sex, respondents strongly recommended (90.0, 100) that gender or sex should be

based solely on an individual's biological makeup. They considered this view as universal, inherently natural, and prescribed by religious beliefs (55.2). Scientifically, respondents emphasized that sex is determined at birth, not by personal feelings (41.8). A small number of respondents still believed in the concept of "gender fluidity" (3.0).

Freedom of Gender Choice. Analyzing the respondents' attitudes towards their freedom of gender choice can reveal either their acceptance or resistance to diverse gender identities and expressions (Rich, 1980). This may reflect on certain proposed concepts such as societal openness or resistance to gender diversity (Nanda, 2014). Present respondents quite disagreed (41.4, 0) with the idea that individuals should be officially and entirely free to choose or declare their gender preference. They argued that an individual's sex and sex organs are determined from conception to birth (66.9). Some suggested vaguely that gender could be a personal choice or environmental right only when accompanied by some sense of responsibility (33.1).

Parental Guidance on Gender. Understanding the respondents' opinions on parental guidance regarding gender, breastfeeding, and abortion can offer insights into the role of family and culture in shaping individual attitudes and choices particularly related to gender and reproductive rights (Fiano-Chesser, 2022). On these issues, the respondents quite disagreed (39.7, 0) with the suggestion that parents should leave to their children the obligation to decide on their sex or gender when they grow older. Instead, they believed that parents should guide their children toward recognizing their biological sexes, which are evident from birth (88.9). A minority argued vaguely for "freedom as to who we are" (11.1). Regarding women's freedom on breastfeeding and abortion, respondents also quite disagreed (35.6, 0) with the idea that women may choose not to breastfeed or even abort their babies. Such decisions were viewed as

sinful, inhumane, immoral, and highly irresponsible (65.3). Exceptions were considered only in cases involving a threat to the mother's life or health (31.5).

Perception of the GE Movement. The respondents' awareness of the existence of the gender movement can help gauge the movement's visibility and impact in the Philippines (Kabeer, 2005). Overall, the study respondents expressed strong opposition (25.2, 0) to the existence of a gender movement in the country. They cited its perceived pointlessness, redundancy, financial burden, and the belief that the Constitution already safeguards equal rights for all (71.7). Some respondents viewed GE as a mere reminder to respect women and other "genders" (18.3). Others emphasized the importance of honoring traditional gender roles in the family and society (10.0).

Degree of Concern about GE

Table 5 reveals the respondents' responses to the third study question, highlighting their concerns and perspectives on various aspects related to GE. This section particularly explores the degree of concern about the various aspects of GE encompassing concerns related to its importance, the numerical imbalances in professions, the intersection of GE and religion, gender competitions, the LGBTI population, rights to breastfeed and abortion, further interest in learning about GE, the elevation of GE as a national priority, economic dependency on gender, and the teaching of GE in schools. The respondents held diverse opinions on these matters, further revealing a range of interesting concerns and perspectives.

Importance of GE. Assessing the respondents' concerns about the importance of GE may reflect their recognition of gender-related issues either as unnecessary societal burdens or significant challenges (Kabeer, 2005). Survey respondents

strongly disagreed (19.0, 0) that GE should be considered a crucial matter deserving of time and resources. They considered GE to be sensational but ultimately trivial, as they believed that the Constitution already addressed its concerns (50.1). Many argued that there are far more pressing issues to address (36.9). However, a minority reasoned that GE is some source of empathy, empowerment for women, and a tool against climate change (13.0).

Male-Female Imbalances. Investigating the concerns about numerical imbalances in professions may reveal the truth about perceptions of gender-based disparities in various fields and sectors (Blau & Winkler, 2021). This study revealed that respondents strongly disagreed (2.8, 0) about giving concerns to numerical imbalances between male and female professionals, deeming such notions as nonsensical and not any cause of worry (53.3). They emphasized that opportunities are open to everyone based on their unique skills. The concept of numerical imbalance was particularly considered far-fetched (46.7).

GE and Religion. Examining how the respondents perceive GE and religion can shed light on potential conflicts or harmonies between religious beliefs and gender-related values (Woodhead, 2014). On this particular issue, the respondents expressed strong concern (80.7, 100) that GE opposes traditional patriarchal Christian beliefs, viewing GE as bizarre and shocking for challenging tradition and religion (70.2). Some respondents simply acknowledged that societal changes may come along with women's empowerment (18.1). A small number of respondents did not have specific ideas (11.7).

Gender Competition. Understanding the concerns related to any gender competition can reveal perceptions of competitiveness or cooperation among genders in various contexts (Eagly, 2000). This study's respondents strongly disagreed

(16.2, 0) with the idea that it is important for women to prove that they can do whatever men can do, or vice versa. They strongly believed that each gender is unique, and such competitions are pointless (80.0). Some respondents emphasized more about the importance of recognizing individuals' capabilities, regardless of gender (20.0). Moreover, regarding the LGBTIs, respondents expressed some concerns (69.4, 100) about their growing population, perceiving them as overacting, troublesome, or individuals going through unnecessary crises (58.6). Some respondents were less concerned about what LGBTIs do with their bodies for as long as they respect others (25.0), while others categorically opined that LGBTIs are unbiblical and disruptors of the natural order (16.4).

Women's Unusual Rights. Analyzing the respondents' concerns about rights concerning breastfeeding and abortion can reveal insights into their real attitudes toward reproductive rights and maternal health (WHO, 2012). Indeed, survey respondents manifested more substantial concerns (86.4, 100) about granting women the right not to breastfeed or even abort their babies. They viewed such acts as crimes against life, morally wrong, and against Christian teachings (78.5). Some respondents suggested that the acceptability of breastfeeding could depend on certain valid justifications, but they strongly opposed abortion (21.5).

Further Interest in GE Ideas. Examining the respondents' interest in learning more about GE may gauge the potential for further GE education and awareness-raising efforts (Duflo, 2012). However, the current respondents expressed a lack of interest (40.5, 0) in learning more about GE, considering it irrational, irrelevant, and a nonsensical waste of money (61.9). Others hinted that simple critical thinking would reveal the lack of benefits derived from using taxpayers' money (38.1).

GE as National Priority. The respondents' opinions regarding the elevation of GE as a national priority may help influence the extent to which the government and policymakers can further prioritize or deprioritize gender-related issues and activities (WEF, 2020). Indeed, this study found that the respondents were deeply worried (90.6100) about GE being elevated as a national priority. They believed that such represents a wasteful allocation of taxes to a nonproblem, with far more important national problems to address (70.3). Many respondents perceived GE as a biased equality movement, focusing solely on women's welfare (18.5). A few respondents suggested alternative uses for GE funds (8.2). Some respondents remained neutral or hinted at potential economic benefits (3.0).

Gender and Economy. The respondents' notion about the economic dependency on gender may reveal about their perception of how gender influences economic opportunities and outcomes (Sen, 1987). Contrary to popularized claims, however, this study found that the respondents strongly disagreed (7.0, 0) with the proposition that the economy depends on the representation of men and women. They asserted that the economy has never been reliant on gender (75.0), rather more on other factors such as corruption, employment opportunities, and leadership (25.0).

Teaching GE in Schools. The respondents' views on the teaching of GE in schools may reflect attitudes towards the inclusion of gender-related education in the curriculum (UNESCO, 2011). The present survey revealed that the respondents were very worried (84.0, 100) about GE being taught to young children in schools, deeming it inappropriate and potentially corrupting (51.8). While some respondents believed that GE education could instill values of respect and equality (25.0), others expressed doubts about the type of respect that might misdirect children away from Christian values (23.2).

Perceived Benefits of GE

Lastly, Table 6 reveals the participants' responses to the final study question, shedding light on their perceptions about the benefits or drawbacks of the GE promotion. This section accordingly summarizes these perceptions. While some respondents mentioned about potential benefits such as equal job opportunities and reduced abuse, majority expressed negative opinions about GE, citing its divisive effects, lack of economic impact, and politicization. Respondents also had revealing views on who benefits from GE, its impact on education, science, traditional beliefs, and religion, and its overall impact on society. Additionally, respondents did not generally believe that they personally benefited from GE, nor see it as beneficial for children or deserving of continued funding from the government.

Benefits of GE. Examining the respondents' perception of the potential benefits of GE, such as equal job opportunities and reduced abuse, can provide insights into the perceived positive outcomes of GE initiatives (Kabeer, 2005). Contrary to this expectation, however, the study respondents strongly denied (22.9, 0) deriving any benefits from the GE promotion, describing them as "none," "unknown," or "imaginary" (80.2). Some mentioned the concept of equal job opportunities, but particularly for women only (18.4). A small minority cited a decrease in women's abuse and the creation of a happier community (1.4).

Negative Effects of GE. Indications of negative opinions about GE, including its divisive effects, can highlight areas where the movement faces criticism and skepticism (Duflo, 2012). On this issue, the study respondents strongly asserted (76.6, 100) that GE has primarily caused factions, conflicts, corrupted values, misallocation of resources (65.2), plus an atmosphere of violence and prejudice, particularly in favoring women (21.7). Some respondents provided ambiguous

responses, considering the GE movement as "positive" but not specifying any known benefits (13.1). Consequently, when asked who truly benefits from the GE promotion, the respondents quite positively (62.1, 100) identified the advocates and promoters themselves, research institutions, women, LGBTIs, and other groups they labeled as "perverts" (76.9). Other respondents had no clear idea (11.9) or would simply mention everybody and certain "oppressed children" (11.2).

Impacts of GE. Investigating the respondents' views on how GE impacts the society on such aspects as economy, politics, education, science, traditional beliefs, and religion can reveal the multifaceted nature of gender-related issues and their implications (Connell, 2014). Regarding the economy, respondents strongly disagreed (22.3, 0) that GE contributes to improving the economy, asserting that it has no connection or relevance to economic growth (81.8). Some mentioned the emergence of "free marriage" and more jobs, particularly for women (15.1), while others remained unsure (3.1). Regarding politics, majority strongly agreed (77.7, 100) that GE issues have become politicized, contributing to campaign funding and elections (65.4). Some had no clear stance or believed that GE was unrelated to politics (23.2). A few mentioned of certain "democratic" aspects as "diversity in leadership" (10.0), and peace (1.4). With regards to education, respondents strongly denied (24.9, 0) that GE has had any positive impact on the educational system, claiming that it has only led to more women, LGBTIs, and GE advocates who corrupt learners (50.1). Others reiterated that there have been no contributions, positive effects, or even relevance to education (25.1). A minority believed that education has become "more equal and open" (13.3). The rest were either unsure or had no particular idea (11.5). Regarding science, respondents strongly disagreed (20.9, 0) with the belief that GE contributes to science, viewing GE as propaganda rather than science and deeming it

unnecessary (83.6). Some acknowledged GE as a social science and pointed out the presence of women scientists (8.4). Others remained unsure (8.0). In the case of tradition and religion, respondents strongly disagreed (10.4, 0) that GE contributes to traditional beliefs or religion, emphasizing that there are no benefits, considering that GE opposes both religion and tradition (81.9). Some had no clear stance (11.8), while others mentioned that some positive changes involve women's increased involvement in churches (6.3).

Finally, regarding GE's overall benefit to society, respondents quite strongly disagreed (21.6, 0) that society has improved because of GE, viewing it as a fake problem that has only worsened society, which could have improved on its own (73.7). Some believe that GE has led to equal opportunities, peace, a safer society, and greater respect for individual rights (16.1). Others had no clear idea (10.2). About personal benefits, the respondents strongly disagreed (18.3, 0) that they individually benefited from the GE movement, describing it as useless, non-beneficial, a waste of time, annoying, and even pestering (73.3). Some revealed that they were just attending required seminars but did not actually agree with the movement (15.1). Some others mentioned additional roles for women, more GAD programs in schools, and more inspiration for LGBTIs (11.6). Particularly, regarding the children, the respondents quite disagreed (28.2, 0) that they would benefit from learning about GE, perceiving GE as pointless, confusing, and potentially harmful with the children lacking appreciation for it (66.7). Yet, some believed that children might learn about equality and tolerance (16.7). Others had no clear idea (16.6).

Government Funds and Support. Exploring whether the respondents believe that GE initiatives deserve continued funding from the government reflects their expectations of government support for such programs (WEF, 2020). Respondents

strongly disagreed (16.5, 0) with the notion that 5% of the government funds should continue to be allocated to GE. They considered this a waste of funds and a form of corruption unworthy of funding while advocating for the redirection of the funds to other government priorities (83.8). Some reiterated same vague assertions about doing it "for the good of society," ensuring "equal rights for all," and promoting "peace" (11.2).

The Respondents' Background

Table 7 provides detailed information about the 21 background (independent) variables that were used to characterize the survey participants. All percentages mentioned in the table are calculated relative to the total of 60 respondents.

Age and Age Groups: The age of the participants ranged from 20 y to 51 y, with a mean of 32 y and a mode of 35 y. This age distribution spans from early adulthood to senescence, predominantly falling within the middle adulthood category.

Origin and Cultural Exposure: A significant portion (70.0%) of the respondents were born outside of Iloilo province, although they had substantial exposure to the Ilonggo culture. Their duration of stay in the province varied from 3 y to 40 y, with an average of 17 y and a mode of 4 y. Approximately 45.0% of the respondents currently resided in Iloilo.

Gender and Marital Status: The survey witnessed a notable gender distribution, with nearly twice as many females (65.0%) participating compared to males (35.0%). A majority of the participants (60.0%) reported being married.

Religion and Worship Mode: In terms of religion, 96.7% of respondents identified themselves as Christians, with the majority being Catholics (76.7%), followed by Protestants (13.3%), and IFI members (6.7%). The remaining 3.3% belonged to the

Table 7

The 21 independent research variables used to characterize the survey respondents. Note that the nominal or categorical variables sex, marital status, and birthplace were coded in numeric terms and are conveniently listed in the next table (Table 8). The complete descriptive and frequency statistics are found in Appendix B

	VAR	DESCRIPTION	MIN	MAX	MEAN	MODE
1	Sex	sex or gender (synonymous)	0	1	0.35	0
2	Age	age	20	51	32.02	35
3	Stat	marital status	1	2	1.60	2
4	Birth	place of birth	0	1	0.30	0
5	Stay	years of residence in Iloilo Province	3	40	16.66	4
6	Add	address in or outside of Iloilo Province	0	1	0.45	0
7	Relgn	religion	1	4	1.40	1
8	Pray	number of church visits per year	0	52	31.13	48
9	Coll	institution of college or tertiary education	0	1	0.28	0
10	GradS	institution of graduate education	0	1	0.67	1
11	Dgree	present degree or level of education	1	3	1.98	2
12	GEsbj	number of GE subjects taken	0	3	0.13	0
13	GEsem	number of GE seminars attended	0	5	2.20	0
14	Traing	type of training apart from academic	0	2	1.00	1
15	Jobnat	nature of present job	1	4	2.07	1
16	Salary	monthly salary, wage or income	15	180	40.23	28
17	HeadF	who is/are considered head(s) of the family	1	4	1.75	1
18	EarnF	who is/are considered bread earner(s) of the family	1	6	2.75	1
19	ChidM	number of male children	0	1	0.32	0
20	ChildF	number of female children	0	2	0.45	0
21	GayX	exposures to LGBTI children, relatives, friends, etc.	0	64	12.52	3

Islamic faith. Regarding church attendance, on average, respondents reported attending church (day of worship) 31 times per year, with a mode of 48.

Education and Additional Training: Around 28.0% of respondents held at least one college degree from the University of the Philippines, while a substantial 67.0% were either in the process of completing or had already completed graduate degrees at the same institution. Their educational achievements included Bachelor of Science (11.7%), Master of Science (78.3%), and Doctorate (10.0%) degrees. Notably, the majority (93.3%) of participants had not undertaken formal courses in gender or GE.

Nevertheless, 71.7% had attended seminars relevant to GE and gender development (GAD). In general, more than half (53.3%) of the participants had received extra academic training, and 23.3% had specific gender education.

Table 8

The levels or categories of the 12 nominal variables from Table 7, tabulated with their corresponding numerical codes used in the statistical processing and analysis

VAR	NUMERICAL CODE						
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Sex	female	male					
Stat		single	married				
Birth	outside Iloilo	in Iloilo					
Add	outside Iloilo	in Iloilo					
Relgn		Catholic	Protestant	Islam	IFI		
Coll	outside UP	in UP					
GradS	outside UP	in UP					
Dgree		BS	MS	PhD			
Traing	none	trained	GE trained				
Jobnat		teach	research	LGU	business		
HeadF		husband	father	single	single mom		
EarnF		husband	father	single	single mom	parent & I	sibling & I

Occupational Background: Participants primarily held professional roles, with the majority being teachers (51.7%). Other professions included businessmen (20.0%), local government unit (LGU) personnel (18.3%), and researchers (10.0%). The average monthly income was ₱40,000, with a mode of ₱28,000.

Family Dynamics: In 63.3% of cases, the husband was recognized as the head of the family. For unmarried participants, other family members, such as the fathers (11.7%), the participants themselves (11.7%), or single mothers (13.3%), assumed this role. The primary breadwinners in the families varied, with husbands (43.3%) being the most common, followed by the participants and either parent (26.7%), single mothers (11.7%), fathers (8.3%), participants themselves (8.3%), or participants with

a sibling (1.7%). The total number of male (31.7%) and female (31.6%) children in the participants' families was nearly equal, although female children were slightly more prevalent in a family.

Exposure to Gay Individuals: Participants reported varying degrees of exposure to gay individuals, including children, siblings, relatives, or friends, as ranging from 0 to 64 individuals. On average, participants reported exposure to 12 such individuals, with a mode of 3.

The Influential Factors

This section serves two important purposes: test the study hypotheses and, concurrently, identify the specific background variables, among the 21 considered, that actually influenced the participants' responses.

The hypotheses formulated in Chapter III aimed to investigate whether any of the 21 independent (background) variables had influenced the survey responses (dependent variable). To achieve this, the averaged responses of 60 respondents across each of the 48 numeric items, denoted by AVE60, were utilized. To analyze the influence of these background variables, two statistical techniques were employed for Hypotheses 1 and 2, respectively, One-Way ANOVA and Multi-regression Analysis.

Regarding Hypothesis 1, ANOVA was used to assess how AVE60 varied in relation to the 21 independent background variables, which characterized the survey participants. Before conducting the analysis, Levene Test was applied to validate the ANOVA assumption of "equal group variances" among the independent variables. Only 12 of the 21 variables passed this screening test. Among these, only three variables further demonstrated significant group differences in the mean responses of the participants. Table 9 presents the complete ANOVA results, including those

variables that did not meet the Levene criteria. It is worth noting that some nonparametric tests can re-evaluate group variances for certain variables, such as Dgree and EarnF (degree level and the breadwinners, see Tables 9 & 11), potentially

Table 9

Results of the Levene and One-Way ANOVA Tests on the 21 independent (background) variables (VAR). A dozen variables passed the Levene test (Sigma > 0.05), but only 3 of them could further detect significant group differences (Sigma < 0.05, 'positive,' last column, bold). Positive results for Age, GayX, EarnF, and Dgree may require further nonparametric evaluation after failing the Levene Test. WTC – weighted trend component resulting from analysis of unequal number of cases

	VAR	LEVENE TEST		ANOVA TEST		
		Sigma	Result	WTC	Sigma	Group Diff.
1	GEsem	0.591	passed	cubic	0.362	
2	ChildM	0.434	passed	linear	0.002	positive
3	Add	0.364	passed	linear	0.485	
4	Stat	0.359	passed	linear	0.000	positive
5	Coll	0.359	passed	linear	0.558	
6	GradS	0.169	passed	linear	0.106	
7	Stay	0.149	passed	cubic	0.099	
8	GESbj	0.144	passed	quadratic	0.012	positive
9	Sex	0.090	passed	linear	0.459	
10	Pray	0.071	passed	cubic	0.659	
11	HeadF	0.059	passed	cubic	0.299	
12	Relgn	0.052	passed	cubic	0.262	
13	Age	0.034	failed	cubic	0.000	positive
14	Birth	0.030	failed	linear	0.113	
15	Traing	0.016	failed	quadratic	0.353	
16	Jobnat	0.015	failed	cubic	0.102	
17	Salary	0.004	failed	cubic	0.801	
18	ChildF	0.001	failed	quadratic	0.155	
19	GayX	0.001	failed	cubic	0.003	positive
20	EarnF	0.001	failed	cubic	0.001	positive
21	Dgree	0.000	failed	quadratic	0.001	positive

revalidating the ANOVA results for these variables. In the interim, only three variables - ChildM, Stat, and GESbj - were seen to significantly influence the survey responses (AVE60). Surprisingly, ChildM and GESbj were not previously known to have multiple

levels. However, it was discovered, after analyzing the data, that ChildM (number of male children) had two levels, i.e., either having one male child or none. GESbj (number of GE subjects taken) also turned out to be multi-levelled, with a noticeable distinction in the data between those who had 1 to 3 GE subjects and those who had none. Stat (marital status) already had two known groupings, unmarried and married, with the former category encompassing unwed and single mothers.

Multi-regression Analysis followed to test Hypothesis 2. Two separate runs were conducted to determine which independent variables could better explain AVE60 using a linear model. The first run included only the factors ChildM, Stat, and GESbj since they passed both the Levene and ANOVA Tests. However, in an effort to improve the search for a more robust model, a second run was carried out, incorporating factors Dgree and HeadF, which exhibited high correlations with the dependent variable (Table 10). Unfortunately, it was found that they merely added to the number of factors that, although could meaningfully explain model variance, could not significantly enhance predictive model performance. Table 11 displays the results of the multi-regression analysis. Based on the R^2 criterion, the highest values were observed in Models 4 and 5. However, further applying the principle of parsimony, Model 4 (ChildM, Stat, GESbj, and Dgree as factors) was selected as most appropriate due to its fewer variables. Consequently, it was established that only four factors, among the 21 background variables, best elucidated the predictive capability of the multi-regression model.

Explaining the Factors

In theory, it is possible to go back to the detailed data to relate every background variable to the survey responses. However, this is way too impractical for

the present study. The averaged response (AV60) proved sufficient in addressing the study objectives. Moreover, in similar token to the linear model assumption in the Conceptual Framework (Chapter III, Section 1), the rest of the background variables

Table 10

Pearson correlations of the averaged response of the survey participants (AVE60) with the background variables. Two-tailed Sigma < 0.5 indicates significant correlations (variables and values in bold)

	VAR	N	Pearson	Sigma
1	Sex	60	-0.097	0.459
2	Age	60	-0.024	0.858
3	Stat	60	-0.490	0.000
4	Birth	60	0.207	0.113
5	Stay	58	0.107	0.425
6	Add	60	0.092	0.485
7	Relgn	60	0.082	0.536
8	Pray	60	0.075	0.570
9	Coll	60	0.077	0.558
10	GradS	60	-0.211	0.106
11	Dgree	60	0.339	0.008
12	GEsbj	60	0.405	0.001
13	GEsem	60	0.091	0.491
14	Traing	60	-0.104	0.428
15	Jobnat	60	0.094	0.474
16	Salary	60	-0.025	0.851
17	HeadF	60	0.275	0.033
18	EarnF	60	0.249	0.055
19	ChidM	60	-0.389	0.002
20	ChildF	60	0.002	0.989
21	GayX	60	0.221	0.090

could be treated as irrelevant “residuals” and did not merit further mention at this juncture. Consequently, this section confines the following explanations to the outcome of the ANOVA and Multi-Regression analyses involving variables ChildM, Stat, GEsbj, and Dgree, the factors found as most influential to the survey responses.

ChildM (Number of Male Children). The GE promotion impressed the respondents that it is a feminist propaganda. Thus, it was conceivable for the predominantly female respondents having male children to view feminist ideas as unappealing. These mothers manifested the usual protective reactions for their only sons (*ChildM* had only 2 levels, 0 or 1). Interestingly, this turned out to be the strongest factor influencing their response.

Table 11

Multi-regression Model Summary. The averaged response of the survey participants (AVE60) was regressed on independent variables ChildM, Stat, GEsbj, Dgree, and HeadF. R – correlation between model and data variations. R² – proportion of variation in the dependent variable explained by the regression model. The best model choice (Model 4) is one with the relatively high value of R² and also contains the fewest variables

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.389	0.151	0.136	9.95511
2	0.509	0.259	0.233	9.37940
3	0.579	0.335	0.299	8.96753
4	0.628	0.394	0.350	8.63449
5	0.628	0.394	0.338	8.71361

1. Predictors: (Constant), ChildM
 2. Predictors: (Constant), ChildM, Stat
 3. Predictors: (Constant), ChildM, Stat, GEsbj
 4. Predictors: (Constant), ChildM, Stat, GEsbj, Dgree
 5. Predictors: (Constant), ChildM, Stat, GEsbj, Dgree, HeadF
- Dependent Variable: AVE60

Stat (Marital Status). This second strongest factor behind the survey responses bears on the first, simply by virtue of the preponderance of married respondents (60% of the predominantly female respondents) and the fact that some unwed and single mothers classified in the analysis as “unmarried” actually also had each a son. Further, it is likely that married Filipino couples will find gender ideas as unnecessarily radical

for traditional families, more so for Christian living. Thus, the presence or absence of a male child in the family also factored strongly in the respondents' responses.

GESbj (Number of GE Subjects Taken). This third influential factor may be construed as a doctrinal influence of gender promotion, which had already become compulsory in schools. The aggressive mainstreaming campaigns in learning institutions have ultimately resulted in courses being taught in schools, apart from seminars and workshops. In this study, this factor made a significant difference in the response of those who had taken 1 to 3 GE subjects as opposed to those who had none.

Dgree (Level of Education). Recall that this variable was only arbitrarily qualified for the Multi-Regression Analysis by virtue of its relatively high correlation with the averaged survey response. It may have parallel effects with GESbj above. The respondents were predominantly UP-educated; some 95% graduated from or were completing their respective degrees at the University of the Philippines. Moreover, 88.3% were at the graduate levels, predominantly MS level. Therefore, while 93.3% had no formal GE courses, e.g., the non-social science majors, many (71.7%) may actually have attended prescribed seminars or trainings related to gender development. This factor influenced the responses to the survey and is attributable to the nationwide mainstreaming effort.

A Synoptic Analysis

The survey involved participants who were responsible middle-aged adults, with an average age of 32 y. They were working professionals, earning a decent monthly averaged income of ₱40,000. Well-educated, they had formal degrees, with most of them either completing or had completed their Master's or PhD degrees

predominantly from the University of the Philippines. Over half had received additional academic training, with almost a quarter being gender-related. A few had taken formal GE courses, but over three-fourths had attended GE or GAD seminars.

Most participants were not originally from Iloilo but had lived there for an average of 17 y. Approximately half of them currently reside in Iloilo. The majority were identified as Christians, predominantly Catholic, with only 3.3% being Muslims. Frequent church visits were common among the participants. The majority acknowledged the husband as the head of the family, while unmarried individuals identified their fathers, themselves, or single mothers with this role. In most cases, the husband was the primary breadwinner, though in some cases, it was either the father, single mother, the participant, or the participant along with a parent or sibling. More than half of the participants were married, and there were almost twice as many females as males. Families tended to have more female children. Participants reported an average of 12 acquaintances or exposures to gay individuals among their children, siblings, relatives, or friends.

Statistical analyses of the participants' background information identified three significant variables that primarily influenced their responses to the survey: ChildM - the number of male children, Stat - marital status, and GESbj - the number of GE subjects taken. When combined with the participants' current degree level (Degree), the set of four variables provided the most robust predictive capability of a multi-regression model used to analyze the survey responses.

With the background profile of the respondents established, the following pertained to their collective opinions of GE respectively of the four study questions:

Level of Understanding. The understanding of GE is fairly widespread, but the claim of GE having achieved equality lacks concrete evidence. People are familiar with

GE through various sources such as online platforms, media, seminars, and personal interactions. The movement is known to primarily focus on promoting women's welfare and address gender-related issues, like their discrimination. However, there is limited awareness of how the 5% budget allocated for the promotion is actually being utilized. Furthermore, there is a common skepticism about GE's claim of improving equality for all, including the LGBT individuals.

Degree of Acceptance. The concepts associated with GE are met with serious resistance as they are perceived to conflict, notably, with traditional beliefs. Traditional gender roles are emphasized, with certain tasks considered more suitable for either men or women. It is argued that the traditional society does not oppress women. However, the non-traditional gender concepts must be rejected in favor of biological sex as sole determinant. Additionally, there is opposition to the idea of allowing children to choose their gender.

Degree of Concern. GE is not considered a top priority; people instead view it as diverting resources from more pressing issues. There is also serious concern that it contradicts religious beliefs and that the increasing visibility of LGBT individuals, particularly in education, have negative consequences. Many concerns arise as reactions to perceived fallacious ideas propagated by the GE campaigns.

Perceived Benefits. The benefits claimed by GE are viewed as highly imaginary and, instead, GE presents more real disadvantages. Thus, the movement is not perceived as contributing to the economy, education, science, or religion. Instead, it is viewed as primarily benefiting political interests and advocacy groups. There are calls to discontinue government funding for GE, which is seen as an expensive but unproductive endeavor.

Lessons from the Interviews

From interviews of the gender experts, it was interesting to note the uniformity of their explanations regarding the supposed benefits of GE. However, what was even more remarkable was the uniformity in their level of understanding regarding the criticisms and counter-criticisms of the advocacy. They also manifested a shared vagueness about why they support GE, especially in opposition to Christianity. Similarly, they appeared to overlook (or ignore) the inconsistencies within the advocacy. These uniform responses suggest a common source of information that has not been critically examined.

One practical implication of these findings is the potential of reducing reliance on the number of experts involved in future studies.

A Concluding Remark

The study findings appreciably diverge from the conventional gender literature in offering insights into Oriental reactions through Filipino respondents. Expecting tangible benefits from the flawed GE advocacy seems unrealistic; instead, examining its adverse effects is essential. Unfortunately, gathering feedback from affected populations remains a big hurdle and ironical given an existing vast literature.

In its current state, the GE movement falls short of promoting genuine equality, instead fostering misleading perceptions. It divides society by elevating women to an unequal status, bestowing them undue privileges, and eroding the traditional Filipino values. Unfortunately, this trend may persist because its goal is to make Filipinos abandon their belief in a male God and embrace the gender ideology. Moreover, apart from consuming significant national resources, GE appears to align with the global agenda of a One World Government, endangering national identities notably within the oriental ASEAN context. Collaboration from Filipino professionals complicates the situation because they comply with foreign elites in embedding the GE ideology into

national laws, thus enabling population control. Unopposed, GE advocates confidently disseminate misinformation through propaganda and legislation.

Drawing from the existing literature, the feminist perspective has precipitated significant shifts in the society. Traditional biological sex is now redefined as a socially "fluid" gender concept, granting women and LGBTIs more decision-making power, even in sensitive areas like breastfeeding and abortion. The framing of women's rights as the "human rights" has practically coerced society to accept and extoll self-perceptions, irrespective of biological reality. Furthermore, GE advocates seriously challenge religious and traditional values.

Gender inequality is a complex issue, and dedicating extensive resources to its nebulous advocacy raises serious questions. Beyond the Philippines, the implications for the oriental ASEAN context are very significant. Oriental nations, often sharing cultural and social similarities, may face similar complications and undesired transformations as GE gains ground. While the motivations behind the movement remain unclear, promoters and advocates appear to benefit, raising further concerns as taxpayers also lack the encouragement to question the movement. In the main, the present study provides important insights into this enigma, pointing to potential serious implications for the broader ASEAN region.

Chapter V

RECOMMENDATIONS OF THE STUDY

This concluding chapter encompasses three sections: Conclusion, Implications, and Recommendations. It revisits the main findings, summarizes the key points, and suggests potential avenues for future research.

Section 1 states the settlement of the study questions. It restates the main findings, summarizes the key points, and suggest some future directions for further investigation.

Section 2 relates the findings to relevant practices and theories.

Section 3 offers practical but crucial suggestions gleaned from the conclusion and implications of the study.

Conclusion

This section presents the final resolution of the study's research questions. The findings rest upon a robust survey conducted among highly qualified respondents, guided by expert opinions, and supported by an extensive body of literature. They offer direct insights into the four study objectives/questions:

1. Respondents exhibited a sufficient understanding of GE.
2. GE was perceived as disruptive, especially due to its clash with traditional beliefs and practices.
3. The GE movement raised unwarranted concerns.
4. The movement incurred high costs without delivering tangible benefits, leaving taxpayers as non-beneficiaries.

Notably, it became evident that the real beneficiaries of GE did not include the affected taxpayers. Furthermore, gender experts themselves hinted that GE ideas originated from foreign sources. Lastly, there was a striking confirmation that public reactions often ran counter to the ideas being aggressively promoted in the GE literature. While these reactions are valuable, they have been largely ignored and not encouraged.

Implications

The practical implications of this study highlight GE as an excellent case for learners to scrutinize the nature of controversial global advocacies. These advocacies serve as opportune tools for nurturing critical thinking skills. In particular, young people can gain insights into the indoctrination process and how it shapes advocates with uniform beliefs.

On theoretical implications, certain theories on emotions and higher-order thinking come into play. The successful implantation of gender ideas in Philippine institutions and the Constitution is a result of rhetorical and psychological devices, discernible through critical learning (Moore & Parker, 2004). Unfortunately, weak Filipino values often succumb to aggressive foreign advocacies (cf. David, 2011; Gripaldo, 2009; Quito, 1994), as these exploit the potent psychology of evoking emotions (e.g., fear, risk, hope, or despair) and transforming them into beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors (Loewenstein, Weber, Hsee, & Welch, 2001; Fritze, Blashki, Burke, & Wiseman, 2008; Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). Fear, as a basic yet intense response, is also selective (Bower, Gilligan, & Monteiro, 1981), conditioned (Rachman, 1977; Begley, Underwood, Wolffe, Smalley, & Interlandi, 2007), and an environmentally significant behavior (Stern, 2000b). In fallacious advocacies, the "fear

appeal" theory posits the risk of dire consequences if the promotion is not successful. This theory relies on threats, motivating individuals to act, often by considering group-think as a safer option (Williams, 2012; Eckart, 2011; Witte & Allen 2000). Indeed, scare tactics have made global advocacies formidable (e.g., Kerr, 2007), and the vulnerability of Filipino values has been highly compromised (David, 2012), prompting their essential psychological revitalization.

Recommendations

The findings of this study pose a serious challenge, particularly to Filipino professionals, urging them to think critically and take action against foreign interventions that adversely impact their population. In particular, the following actions are imperative:

1. Conduct a comprehensive cost-benefit analysis of the GE promotion.
2. Launch an extensive campaign against misleading advocacies.
3. Promote critical thinking skills in educational institutions.
4. Initiate psycho-social studies regarding the exploitation of Filipino values.
5. Implement values education programs for professionals.
6. Reinforce traditional beliefs, practices, and nationalism as a cornerstone of national identity.
7. Encourage replications of this study and its cross-validations with diverse feedback.

As a final source of inspiration, it is important to recognize that the journey toward reversing adverse impacts to the Filipino society is long and arduous. However, every Filipino must realize that he bears the responsibility for the society's predicament; he has the capacity to bring about positive developments.

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Appendices

APPENDIX A
The Survey Questionnaire
(Background, Survey Proper, and Instructions)

CONTROL No.		SAMPLE DATA (FICTITIOUS)	
NOTE: To be replaced by respondent's data. Write NA if the response to an item is Not Applicable.			
NAME	Juan C. Cruz		
GENDER	male		
AGE	27		
STATUS	married		
BIRTHPLACE	Moderna Town, Iloilo		
YEARS OF STAY IN ILOILO PROVINCE	6		
CURRENT ADDRESS	123 Paha St., Litana Viejo, Iloilo		
CONTACT No. AND EMAIL	0999771111; myemail@mailme.com		
SKIN COMPLEXION	fair brown, hairy		
GENERAL BODY BUILT	thin, dark, tall, and muscular		
RELIGION	Protestant (Evangelical)		
CHURCH VISITS/YEAR	48		
PRE-SCHOOL	NA		
KINDERGARTEN SCHOOL	Santo Santissima Creative School		
PRIMARY SCHOOL	South Kabataan Elementary School		
HIGH SCHOOL	Iloilo Integrated Scientific High School		
TERTIARY SCHOOL AND MAJOR	Panay Ecumenical Colleges; B.S. Mechanical Engineering		
GRADUATE SCHOOL AND MAJOR	University of Graduate Colleges; M.S. Mathematics Education		
No. GENDER AND RELATED SUBJECTS TAKEN	0		
No. GENDER AND RELATED SEMINARS	1		
LIST IMPORTANT TRAININGS	Teachers Workshop, Dara City; Seminar in Machines, Punta Bato City; 3-month Seminar Program in Ethics, Sheba Town		
LIST OF ORGANIZATIONS	Judo-kan Association of Iloilo; PTA- Nuevo Chapter; Science Club, University of Clubs, Nuevo; Men and Women's Club		
JOB AND POSITION	teacher; associate professor 2		
NATURE OF THE JOB	teaching college students; School Counselor		
EMPLOYER	Private School of La Fortuna, Province of Camansi		
BASIC SALARY/MONTH	35,000		
INCOME SOURCE IF UNEMPLOYED	NA		
JOB AND POSITION OF SPOUSE	rural worker; Extension Worker 4		
NATURE OF THE JOB (SPOUSE)	extension work in rural communities, liason work for the organization		
EMPLOYER (SPOUSE)	Save the Equality of Rights Foundation, Inc., Viejo Branch		
BASIC SALARY/MONTH (SPOUSE)	30,000		
WHO IS THE HEAD OF THE FAMILY	myself		
WHO IS BREAD EARNER OF THE FAMILY	myself and spouse		
No. MALE CHILDREN	2		
No. FEMALE CHILDREN	1		
No. LGBTI CHILDREN	0		
No. LGBTI SIBLINGS	0		
No. LGBTI RELATIVES	0		
No. LGBTI FRIENDS	1		
No. LGBTI CO-WORKERS	4		
MAIN HOBBIES	martial arts; reading; hiking; photography; hanging out with officemates; tennis meetings		
PARTICULAR LIKES	honest people; Korean food; musical shows; political discussions; electronic gadgets		
PARTICULAR DISLIKES	pets; hypocrisies; modern dance; spicy meals; noisy parties; foul smell		
USUAL HANGOUTS	beaches; Library of Antiques; Café de la Choco; Tennis Club of Viejo; billiard salons		
RESPONDENT'S REMARKS - IF ANY	(Write additional remarks or comments here - if any.)		
DATE ACCOMPLISHED	14-Jun-21		
<END>			
THANK YOU VERY MUCH!			

CONT No.

Name

Date

INSTRUCTIONS:

The main items in this questionnaire only require numeric responses in percentage (from 0 to 100%), which correspond to a "NO" to "YES" (or "DISAGREE" to "AGREE") scale. Just select and write a number between 0 to 100 that matches your response. Please see figure below for a visual interpretation. The scoring scheme provides for a median response (NEUTRAL or undecided) plus a desirable wide range of in-between choices, which will improve your response accuracy. In the case of textual responses (or explanations), blank spaces are provided. As much as possible, supply the blank spaces only with short and telegraphic sentences or just a few intelligible phrases or keywords at the most. Thank you for your time and effort!

Example: Do you like to drink milk?

An answer of 0 means NO (disagree), 100 means YES (agree), 50 means NEUTRAL (or does not really care drinking milk or not), and 80 means more likely drinking milk (or agrees to drinking milk) than, say, 15.

A LEVEL OF UNDERSTANDING OF GENDER EQUALITY:	
1	Do you know what is gender equality? (0-100%)
	Briefly, what is it about?
2	In terms of percentage, how much do you actually know about gender equality? (0-100%)
	Source of information, if any:
3	Are you also aware that gender equality is all about promoting women's welfare? (0-100%)
	Briefly clarify, if necessary:
4	Is gender different from sex? (0-100%)
	Their difference(s), if any:
5	Are lesbians, gays, bisexuals, transgenders, and intersexuals (LGBTIs) other kinds of gender or sex? (0-100%)
	Your comments, if any?
6	Are you aware of some gender issues or problems? (0-100%)
	Enumerate some, if any:
7	Do you know that 5% of the budget of government agencies is mandated for the promotion of gender equality? (0-100%)
	Your source of information, if any:
8	Do you know how the funds for gender equality program are being spent? (0-100%)
	Details of the spending, if any:
9	Do you know what 'equality' is all about in gender equality? (0-100%)
	If so, briefly explain:
10	Is gender equality the cause or origin of equal rights of and opportunities for men and women in our society? (0-100%)
	Briefly clarify, if necessary:
11	Is gender equality also the cause or origin of equal rights of and opportunities for LGBTIs in our society? (0-100%)
	Briefly clarify, if necessary:
12	Does the Constitution speak of equality for all, whether men or women, including the LGBTIs? (0-100%)
	Briefly clarify, if necessary:

B DEGREE OF ACCEPTANCE OF GENDER EQUALITY:	
1	Are there roles, tasks, or functions in the society that are better performed by men than women, or vice versa? (0-100%)
	Example(s) for men, if any:
	Example(s) for women, if any:
2	Do you still accept that fathers - and not mothers - must be treated as heads of their respective families? (0-100%)
	Why do you think so?
3	Does our society actually favor men over women? (0-100%)
	Briefly clarify, if necessary:
4	Do you agree that women are being oppressed, abused, or marginalized in our society? (0-100%)
	Briefly clarify, if necessary:
5	Must women be treated as a separate special sector of our society like orphans, indigents, senior citizens, or PWDs? (0-100%)
	Why/Why not?
6	Must our society specially promote awareness of violence against women only? (0-100%)
	Why/Why not?
7	Is it alright to have more gender or sex categories other than the traditional male and female? (0-100%)
	Why/Why not?
8	Do you accept that the gender or sex of an individual be based only on biological makeup? (0-100%)
	Why/Why not?
9	Must an individual be officially and totally free to choose and declare his/her gender of preference? (0-100%)
	Why/Why not?
10	Must parents agree that their child's sex or gender be decided only by him/her when he/she grows old enough? (0-100%)
	Why/Why not?
11	To protect their health, can women choose, for example, not to breastfeed, or even abort a baby? (0-100%)
	Why/Why not?
12	Do you agree that there must be a gender equality movement in our country? (0-100%)
	Why/Why not?

C DEGREE OF CONCERN ABOUT GENDER EQUALITY:	
1	Is gender equality a crucial matter that you must spend time and resources on? (0-100%)
	Why/Why not?
2	Do you worry whenever there are more male than female politicians, businessmen, teachers, heroes, musicians, etc.? (0-100%)
	Why/Why not?
3	Are you worried that gender equality actually disapproves of the patriarchal (traditional) Christian religion? (0-100%)
	Why/Why not?
4	Is it really important for women to prove that they can do whatever men can do, or vice versa? (0-100%)
	Why/Why not?
5	Are you getting concerned about the growing numbers of LGBTIs? (0-100%)
	Why/Why not?
6	Will you be worried if women are given the rights not to breastfeed or the rights to even abort a baby? (0-100%)
	Why/Why not?
7	Are you generally interested in knowing more about gender equality? (0-100%)
	Why/Why not?
8	Are you worried that gender equality is being elevated as a national priority problem? (0-100%)
	Why/Why not?
9	Is the economy truly dependent on whether or not men and women are equally represented in the society? (0-100%)
	Why/Why not?
10	Do you care if gender equality is taught in schools to your young children? (0-100%)
	Why/Why not?
11	Are you worried with the fact that a part of your taxes goes to the promotion of gender equality? (0-100%)
	Why/Why not?
12	Is gender equality as worrisome as the country's problems on corruption, poverty, and criminality? (0-100%)
	Why/Why not?

D PERCEIVED BENEFITS OF GENDER EQUALITY:

1 Have there been benefits (if any) derived from promoting gender equality in our country? (0-100%)

If any, enumerate some:

2 On the other hand, have been there any bad effects (if any) derived from promoting gender equality? (0-100%)

If any, enumerate some:

3 Do you know who are truly benefiting from the promotion of gender equality (if any)? (0-100%)

If any, enumerate some:

4 Do you think that gender equality is really improving our economy? (0-100%)

How/How not?

5 Do you think that gender equality is also benefiting politics? (0-100%)

How/How not?

6 Do you think that gender equality is truly benefiting our educational system? (0-100%)

How/How not?

7 Do you think that gender equality is contributing to science? (0-100%)

How/How not?

8 Do you think that gender equality is benefiting your traditional beliefs or religion? (0-100%)

How/How not?

9 Has our society actually improved because of the gender equality movement? (0-100%)

How/How not?

10 Have you personally benefited from the gender equality movement? (0-100%)

How/How not?

11 Will children benefit from learning gender equality? (0-100%)

How/How not?

12 Must the government continue spending its 5% budget for gender equality because it is worth our money? (0-100%)

Why/Why not?

THANK YOU VERY MUCH!

APPENDIX B

Descriptive Statistics

RESPONDENTS' BACKGROUND STATISTICS																						
	Sex	Age	Stat	Birth	Stay	Add	Relgn	Pray	Coll	Grads	Dgree	GfSbj	Gfsem	Tring	Jobnat	Salary	Headf	Earnf	ChldM	Chldf	GayX	
N	Valid	60	60	60	58	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60
	Missing	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	0.35	32.02	1.60	0.30	16.66	0.45	1.40	31.13	0.28	0.67	1.98	0.13	2.20	1.00	2.07	40.23	1.75	2.75	0.32	0.45	12.52	
SE of Mean	0.062	0.678	0.064	0.060	1.815	0.065	0.109	2.210	0.059	0.061	0.061	0.073	0.243	0.089	0.159	3.462	0.144	0.229	0.061	0.093	1.530	
Median	0.00	32.00	2.00	0.00	9.50	0.00	1.00	36.00	0.00	1.00	2.00	0.00	2.00	1.00	1.00	32.50	1.00	2.00	0.00	0.00	9.00	
Mode	0	35	2	0	4	0	1	48	0	1	2	0	0	1	1	28	1	1	0	0	3	
Std. Deviation	0.481	5.255	0.494	0.462	13.824	0.502	0.848	17.116	0.454	0.475	0.469	0.566	1.885	0.689	1.233	26.819	1.114	1.772	0.469	0.723	11.851	
Variance	0.231	27.610	0.244	0.214	191.107	0.252	0.719	292.965	0.206	0.226	0.220	0.321	3.553	0.475	1.521	719.241	1.242	3.140	0.220	0.523	140.457	
Skewness	0.645	0.451	-0.419	0.895	0.399	0.206	2.224	-0.432	0.986	-0.725	-0.060	4.657	0.314	0.000	0.543	3.863	1.126	0.280	0.809	1.293	2.429	
SE of Skewness	0.309	0.309	0.309	0.309	0.314	0.309	0.309	0.309	0.309	0.309	0.309	0.309	0.309	0.309	0.309	0.309	0.309	0.309	0.309	0.309	0.309	
Kurtosis	-1.640	1.804	-1.889	-1.241	-1.656	-2.026	4.039	-1.329	-1.063	-1.526	1.861	21.660	-1.295	-0.826	-1.406	16.445	-0.308	-1.666	-1.394	0.195	7.647	
SE of Kurtosis	0.608	0.608	0.608	0.608	0.618	0.608	0.608	0.608	0.608	0.608	0.608	0.608	0.608	0.608	0.608	0.608	0.608	0.608	0.608	0.608	0.608	
Range	1	31.00	1	1.00	37.00	1.00	3	52.00	1.00	1.00	2	3.00	5.00	2	3	165.00	3	5	1.00	2.00	64.00	
Minimum	0	20.00	1	0.00	3.00	0.00	1	0.00	0.00	0.00	1	0.00	0.00	0	1	15.00	1	1	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Maximum	1	51.00	2	1.00	40.00	1.00	4	52.00	1.00	1.00	3	3.00	5.00	2	4	180.00	4	6	1.00	2.00	64.00	

APPENDIX C

Reliability, Factor, and Discriminant Analyses

Appendix C.1. *A re-computation of the reliability of 48 numeric items using 60 respondents. Shown are six Lambda estimates by the Guttman method, the third of which ($R=0.827$) corresponds to the popular Alpha reliability.*

Reliability Statistics

Lambda	1	.810
	2	.896
	3	.827
	4	.716
	5	.851
	6	.998
N of Items		48

The covariance matrix is calculated and used in the analysis.

Appendix C.2. *A principal component analysis of 60 responses for each of the 48 numeric items of the questionnaire. The 1st, 2nd, and 5th columns reveal the 10 significant components also visible in the left portion of the scree plot (inset). Components 1 to 4 already explains about 70% of the total data variance (7th column). Outputs were derived using the SPSS statistical software (SPSS, 1998).*

Appendix C.3. The classification of 48 survey items corresponding to Figure 4. None of the items was misclassified under any other irrelevant construct. The phrase “100% correctly classified” means that the cases were originally assumed under the right construct. Output was derived using the SPSS software (SPSS, 1998).

Classification Results^a

		SECT	Predicted Group Membership				Total
			LOU	DOA	DOC	PBE	
Original	Count	LOU	12	0	0	0	12
		DOA	0	12	0	0	12
		DOC	0	0	12	0	12
		PBE	0	0	0	12	12
%		LOU	100.0	.0	.0	.0	100.0
		DOA	.0	100.0	.0	.0	100.0
		DOC	.0	.0	100.0	.0	100.0
		PBE	.0	.0	.0	100.0	100.0

a. 100.0% of original grouped cases correctly classified.